

CO₂-SPICER - CO₂ Storage Pilot In a CarbonatE Reservoir

TO01000112-V7 Final technical report of the CO₂-SPICER project

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1 INTRODUCTION

The CO₂-SPICER project aimed at preparation of a pilot CO₂ storage in a depleted oil and gas field Zar-3 in the SE Czech Republic. The project started on 1st November 2020 and ended on 30th April 2024. Four partners from the Czech Republic and one from Norway participated in the project under the leadership of the Czech Geological Survey. The partner's acronyms are in Tab. 1-1.

Tab. 1-1: Acronyms of Project Partners used in the report

Project Partner	Acronym
Czech Geological Survey	CGS
MND a.s.	MND
NORCE Norwegian Research Centre AS	NORCE
VSB – Technical University of Ostrava	VSB
Institute of Geophysics of the Czech Academy of Sciences	GFU

The project was divided into 10 Work Packages (WP, Fig. 1-1). Each Work Package had its clearly defined leader, objectives, description of work and planned results. Work packages were structured into Tasks, each with a defined Task leader and deliverables.

Fig. 1-1: Project structure of CO₂-SPICER.

The activities followed the document “Project content & Detailed description of Work Packages” in the Attachment 5 to the Project application. The project structure and the works in each Work Package and Task cover the pieces of knowledge required by the European and Czech legislation regarding the Carbon Storage. The time-line was designed from the beginning till the end to provide the results in the right order with mutual links and the follow-up works.

The project had three governing bodies – the General Assembly, Management Board and End-User Group. All partners involved in the project had one representative in the General Assembly, where the crucial issues were dealt with periodically. The Project Coordinator with the Management Board members met once a month, checked the progress made in each WP and outlined the next steps.

The End-User Group was formed during the Final Projects Conference in Praha and included industrial companies producing greenhouse gas emissions, such as cement plants, lime producers, steel companies, as well as the Ministry of the Environment and Ministry of Industry and Trade. They showed interest in the project results including the experience with the preparation of the first CO₂ storage in the subsurface in the Czech Republic.

A few minor parts of the work requiring special knowledge exceeding the competence of consortium partners were sub-contracted, namely “Well integrity logging” and “Feasibility study on applicability of seismic methods for CO₂ plume monitoring”.

Data gathering and consolidation (Chapter 2 – WP1) prepared suitable data sets required for the description, assessment and screening of the Zar-3 pilot storage site, which have been used as inputs for the three-dimensional static geological model of the storage complex (WP2), dynamic modelling (WP3), risk assessment (WP6) and monitoring (WP7). The required data have been obtained from both publicly available sources (in particular CGS databases) and the archive and databases of the industrial Project Partner and current the Žarošice field operator – MND. The data included maps, sections, well logs, core sample descriptions, well integrity logging and were uploaded to the project geodatabase. It was available online for all Project Partners, respecting, at the same time, the access rights, limited in some cases by the provisions of the Non-disclosure Agreement between MND and research partners of the project. Set of thematic maps of the CO₂ Zar-3 storage site were prepared as N_{map} type in the S42 coordinate system with 14 layers, such as geomorphology, land-use, mineral resources, soil maps. The project results have been transferred to the ZENODO publically accessible repository on internet according to the Data Management Plan.

3D geological model of the storage complex (Chapter 3 – WP2) was focussed on precise geometry of the lithostratigraphic unit surfaces and storage reservoir properties. It was based on interpretations of the seismic and other geophysical data, regional geology, well logs and mud logs acquired within WP1. Fracture intensity distributions were analysed using FMA method of Schlumberger. All the results were provided for the reservoir dynamic modelling in the WP3. Detailed modelling of the overburden seal horizons was used in the risk assessment of the potential leakage to the shallow subsurface and surface in the WP6.

Dynamic modelling and simulations (Chapter 4 – WP3) built the full-field reservoir model of the planned storage site verified by the history match of the recorded oil, water and gas production. Inputs from WP4 Geomechanics and WP5 Geochemistry were used as inputs. Alternative options of the pilot CO₂ injection were simulated for the fractured carbonate reservoirs. Sub-horizontal and base parallel gridding was used. After numerous iterations, permeability distribution matched the pressure and temperature data. The ability of the reservoir to accept injected fluid was verified by an on-site Step-rate-test. The outcomes, particularly CO₂ saturation changes during the pilot injection, were used as input in the Seismic monitoring study in WP7 and the Injection scenarios elaborated in the WP8.

Geomechanical characteristics of the storage complex (Chapter 5 – WP4) were evaluated based on determination of ultrasonic stiffness and strengths of the reservoir and sealing rocks. Conclusions were made on the failure envelope describing the stress states, at which irreversible rock failures occur, and conditions necessary to keep the storage of the injected CO₂ safe. The effect of changes in fluid pressure during storage and the effect of cooling by the cold supercritical CO₂ were evaluated in respect to changes in the effective stress.

Geochemistry (Chapter 6 – WP5) covered characteristics of fluids, microbial consortia, rocks and fluid-rock interactions. The oil analytical results provided standard technological oil properties, molecular fingerprints, oil type, thermal maturity, co-sourcing, biodegradation and changes due to water washing in the reservoir. The gas chemical composition focussed on methane and CO₂, gas typing, thermal maturity, microbiological effects, mixing, migration alterations, H₂S occurrence and risk assessment (WP6). Formation water data served for predictions of fluids miscibility, CO₂ dissolution, phase equilibria and simulation of fluid flow in the reservoir in the dynamic model (WP3). Microbiological study summarized the current knowledge about microbial consortia living in oil and gas fields. Chemical and microscopic analyses of the reservoir and seal rocks documented details of their origin and dual character of the fracture and vuggy (cavernous) porosity used in dynamic modelling (WP3). Microporosity is dominant in all caprocks. The general conclusion was, that the Zar-3 storage complex has been efficiently sealed and would be a safe storage site. Experiments on CO₂-fluid-rock interactions were carried out in the reaction chambers and models were calculated using the Geochemist's Workbench (GWB) program. For all reservoir and cap rock samples, the most important chemical processes included dissolution of carbonates (calcite and dolomite) and microcline due to acidification of the formation water during the injection of CO₂ into the reservoir, followed by formation of secondary carbonates in the remote future. Minor porosity changes were predicted by the models associated with the CO₂ injection to the reservoir. The results were used in the dynamic modelling (WP3).

Risk assessment (Chapter 7 – WP6) was focussed on identification of hazards related to leakage from the storage site based on guidance in the EU CCS Directive 2009/31/EC as well as in the Czech Act No 85/2012 Sb. Following aspects were analysed: potential leakage pathways, flux rates, critical controls and secondary effects of storage of CO₂ and other factors which could pose a hazard to human health or the environment. Risk assessment was evaluated using the geochemistry, geomechanics and well integrity logging.

Monitoring (Chapter 8 – WP7) included a review of monitoring methods and their applicability, soil gas survey, seismology, shallow groundwater hydrology and modelling, reservoir containment and stability. The experience from the base line (pre-storage) works was used as the basis for the formulation of the Storage site monitoring plan (SMP), which is one of the main obligations of a storage site operator, both during site operations and after site closure, and would become an important document for the application for a CO₂ injection permit. As an input, the SMP involves international CCS project guidelines, international scientific literature and recommendations from individual reports of the CO₂-SPICER project.

Future scenarios of the Zar-3 site development (Chapter 9 – WP8) included design of the surface and subsurface facilities for the selected pilot site. Whole value chain analysis was necessary in order to identify potential gaps between the costs associated with capture, transport and site development costs. Preliminary estimates were prepared of the required capital costs and operative expenses related to both the pilot project scenario and full scale CO₂-EOR including storage application at the Zar-3 field.

Communication and dissemination (Chapter 10, WP9) aimed at good information about the project objectives, implementation, results, events and the bilateral Czech-Norwegian cooperation. The work was guided by the project Communication plan. The progress on the planned works was presented at regular project meetings, workshops, international

conferences and the final conference in March 2024. Further activities included the updated project website, Newsletter, information leaflet, radio podcasts and press releases.

Project management and reporting (Chapter 11 – WP10) included coordination and activities that ensured a smooth run of the work packages and timely preparation of the results. The partner's roles and duties were defined in the Partnership Agreement. The top level decisions were made by the General Assembly, where each partner institution had one representative. The Project Coordinator with the Management Board (MB) members met on a monthly basis, checked the progress made in each WP and outlined the next steps. Minutes of the MB meetings are recorded in one of the deliverables. Other activities further included ongoing economic s and communication with the TA ČR - Fund Operator. The End-user Group served as the main project target group – industrial companies interested in the CCS technology, policy makers and regulators, e.g. the Czech Ministry of Industry and Trade, Ministry of the Environment, Heidelberg Group - Českomoravský cement a.s. and Association of Lime Producers.

2 DATA GATHERING AND CONSOLIDATION

The main goal of this project part (WP1) was to obtain suitable data for the description, assessment and screening of the Zar-3 pilot storage site. These data sources were used as inputs during the development of a three-dimensional static geological model of the storage site and complex (WP2), dynamic modelling (WP3), risk assessment (WP6) and monitoring (WP7). The required data have been obtained from both publicly available sources (in particular CGS database) and the archive and databases of the industrial Project Partners (and current Zar-3 field operator) MND. All collected data were consolidated and unified (Task 1.1). Task 1.2 was reserved for collection and analysis of well cores. The overview of all collected data was kept using a dedicated project geodatabase and GIS repository (Task 1.3).

Work under WP1 started at the beginning of the project in November 2020 and was carried out according to the plan up to April 2024; some issues were caused by the tornado, which destroyed the MND's core repository in Lužice in June 2021. Its consequences, in particular the complete loss of part of the core material and the inaccessibility of the core repository due to reconstruction works, affected the work on the project but caused only minor delays.

2.1 Collection, consolidation and unification of existing data, site characterization (Task 1.1)

The existing (geographical, geological, geophysical etc.) data gathered in frame of Task 1.1 were prepared and used as the main inputs for the development of the static geological model (WP2) and other project activities in WP6 and WP7. In accordance with valid carbon dioxide legislation (Act 85/2011 Sb., Annex "Criteria for the characterization and assessment of the planned storage complex and surrounding area", part 1. "Basic data for characterization and assessment of the planned storage complex and surrounding area"), the following maps and data sets have been prepared:

- Surface geological map of the Zar-3 site on a scale 50,000
- Map of areas of interest and administrative division (incl. 3D seismic area)
- Map of territorial (NATURE 2000) and species nature conservation
- Map of territorial system of ecological stability
- Map of selected species and international nature conservation
- Hydrogeology map (incl. drinking water sources)
- Map of mineral resource deposits (hydrocarbon fields and UGSs)
- Map of industrial CO₂ emission sources
- Map of geohazards (identified landslides)
- Map of biogeography and climate
- Hydrography and geomorphology map
- Land use map
- Soil map of the Czech Republic on a scale of 50,000

- Map of agriculture land protection classes
- Map of conflict of interests (incl. linear construction)
- Dataset of relevant deep wells (wellhead coordinates, trajectory, casing design)
- Dataset of well logs (both digital and graphic) and check-shot survey (velocity data)
- Dataset of mudlogs (drill cuttings analysis)

Maps listed above formed a part of the project result TO01000112-V3 (Set of thematic maps of the CO₂ Zar-3 storage site; type N_{map}) that was submitted in December 2023.

The most important sources of available geological data represented information from existing wells and historical geological survey reports. The area of the Zar-3 site (and surrounding) comprised a total of 22 deep wells (including site-tracks); 14 of them penetrated the reservoir itself; four of them were side-tracks. Most of the wells were deviated or horizontal. In addition, about 30 shallow hydro- or engineering-geology wells were drilled in the area of interest, with different amounts of available documentation. Shallow wells represented input for shallow groundwater monitoring (WP7) while the deep wells have been used for construction of the geological model (WP2). All available valuable deep-well data were compiled and quality-checked, and put into a user-friendly format in both graphic and table forms.

Seismic data (especially 3D seismic) represented the key piece of information and data source for the development of the 3D geological model (WP2). Time and depth sections along seismic reflection profiles (2D seismic) in the site area have been retrieved from CGS geophysical database and their original geological interpretation was evaluated and updated to the current level of knowledge. The data and their interpretation were prepared for import into the 3D geological model (WP2). Project Partner MND provided the project team with three-dimensional (3D) seismic data for the Zar-3 field and surrounding area. The use of these data was covered by a Non-disclosure agreement between MND and other Project Partners. The data block covered the whole site area and its vicinity, allowing the project team to prepare a detailed fault and structural plan of the net storage itself, as well as the whole storage complex (storage site and surrounding area in sense of valid legislation). The main interpretation work was carried out directly in the 3D modelling environment within Task 2.1 in WP2.

Well-log data were available for 18 wells at the Zar-3 field and its vicinity; the minimum extent of used methods is resistivity, spontaneous polarization and gamma-ray logs at older wells but more complex logging is available for the younger ones. Check-shot surveys have been registered in 3 wells. All well-log records were provided by MND in digital form, mostly in the LAS format. After a quality check the data have been visualized in a user-friendly graphic form (see Fig. 2-1) and provided to the project team. In addition, all well-log curves have been processed into a consolidated data file to be:

- directly imported into the modelling tools for the 3D geological model (WP2);
- used for subsequent interpretation, including, in particular, porosity and clay content calculations, which will serve as input for distribution of reservoir properties in the 3D model (WP2).

A special data source was represented by the so called “mudlog”, i.e. analysis of drill cuttings separated from the drilling mud. These data have been collected in graphic form for all reservoir wells and have been summarized in a partial database. These data provided

very good information about lithology along the borehole. From the original well and Geoservice final reports, some technical drilling parameters, like weight on bit (WOB), rotation of drilling bit, velocity of drilling (min/m, m/h), pressure and true vertical depth were evaluated for each reservoir well. Such data were especially valuable for geomechanical assessment of rocks building the storage complex (WP4). Temperature and pressure history (2001 - 2021) data were available only from the well ZA3. These data provided basis for heat flow modelling and temperature distribution in dynamic modelling (WP3).

Fig. 2-1: Example of graphic representation of well-log curves (well UH9).

Data on oil and gas shows, pumping test results, drill stem test (“tester”) have been compiled from the archival reports and a specialized database part has been prepared for WP5 – geochemistry.

Well design data (casing, perforation, cement plugs) have been prepared as a basis for risk evaluation (WP6) for all 22 deep wells (site-tracks including). For abandoned wells, the well design after abandonment has been compiled, including graphic representation (see Fig. 2-2). A special borehole measurement known as “cement log” (sonic logging focused on presence and thickness of annular cement) represented another data source for risk assessment and evaluation.

Fig. 2-2: Example of graphic representation of well design (abandoned well UH12).

During 2021-2022, a basic site characterization was ongoing with the purpose to gather and process the main geographical and geological data on the storage site (result R1.2, December 2022). In doing so, the CGS team was using publicly available and departmental maps, maps of protected areas, data from CGS Geofond databases, as well as data from MND archives. In addition, data in the possession of organizations founded by the Ministry of Agriculture and the Ministry of Environment of the Czech Republic were included. A field survey comprising basic geological, geographical and pedological (soil) mapping has been performed. All produced maps have been integrated – together with other thematic site maps created in WP7 - in the main result TO01000112-V3 “Set of thematic maps of the CO₂ Zar-3 storage site” (type N_{map}, December 2023). Fig. 2-3 shows an example from this set of maps.

Fig. 2-3: Land use map of the wider area of Zar-3 CO₂ storage site.

The data described above, together with all additional data gathered, measured or otherwise established in the course of the project, were stored in the project geodatabase (a spatial geodatabase in which geographical and spatial information are stored for future reference) that was created as part of Task 1.3. To ensure that all project data share a unified geographic framework, a basic coordinate system (S42) was defined at the start of the project. All project data have been and will be converted to this system.

2.2 Overview of available cores and their documentation, sampling selection (Task 1.2)

This Task represented activity oriented at well cores availability in MND core repository (see Fig 2-4). The goal was to access suitable core and cuttings materials for further analyses and take core samples needed for various laboratory experiments and tests (WP4, WP5).

The first phase of core inspection (February - May 2021) suggested that the core repository included sufficient reservoir rock cores, while caprock cores were available only from the well ZA3 and the old wells UH6 - UH16. During the first phase, 62 core boxes containing cores from wells located in the Zar-3 site and its vicinity have been selected. Core samples of selected cores have been taken for follow-up laboratory experiments in frame of WP4 (geomechanics) and WP5 (geochemistry). For geomechanic experiments, only 17 core boxes were identified as suitable. The selected core boxes and taken core samples were registered in a special “master table” to keep the overviews and see the progress of utilization of samples and results of laboratory experiments.

Fig. 2-4: Selection of suitable cores in MND core repository.

Search for additional samples of caprock from both Zar-3 site and adjacent fields (e.g. Uhřice field) was interrupted in June 2021 due to the damage of the core repository building by tornado; this work restarted in June 2022. The “second campaign” of core sampling was mainly oriented at caprock samples, since the evaluation of the first set of geomechanical experiments in WP4 revealed insufficient amount of information from caprock. Within this second campaign, eight additional core boxes were selected for sampling. The selection of suitable rock cores was very difficult because many core boxes were destroyed during the tornado in 2021. Some of the “newly” selected core boxes originated from wells from analogue sites in wider area of Zar-3, providing core material from geological formations analogous to those present at Zar-3 site.

At the end of 2022, a collection of cuttings (rock fragments separated from drilling mud) from well ZA3 was prepared by MND and provided to CGS and NORCE for further analyses that was mainly served as input for assessment of caprock integrity within risk assessment (WP6).

During 2023, the special “master table”, covering all selected core boxes and taken core samples, was updated. As a result, two separated “master tables” were created; one of them was arranged according to the “mother” well, the second version of “master table” was arranged according to the stratigraphy of cores. Tab. 2-1 represents cut-out from the “master table” arranged according to “mother” well.

Tab. 2-1: Cut-out from the “master table” arranged according to the “mother” well

Well	Core	Box	Sample name	Sample X (S42)	Sample Y (S42)	Photograph
name	No	No	(well_MD_C_B_from_to)			
ZA6A	1	1	ZA6A_1929_1_1_50_65	3644275,16	5437366,08	
		2	ZA6A_1929_1_2_31_59	3644275,22	5437365,97	
		3	ZA6A_1929_1_3_80_90	3644275,32	5437365,76	
		4	ZA6A_1929_1_4_70_85	3644275,39	5437365,64	

Archival data on oil, gas and water properties were collected as complementary input in WP5 (geochemistry), in addition to the new samples taken from fluids produced by the deep wells that have been subject of laboratory analyses in WP5. Production history data (2001 – 2021, covered by the Non-disclosure Agreement) for oil and gas per production well have been collected and prepared for use in history matching in WP3 (dynamic modelling) and WP8 (future site development).

2.3 Creation of a project geodatabase (database + GIS) (Task 1.3)

In Task 1.3, the CGS project team has designed and prepared a geodatabase to host data gathered in Task 1.1 and well core data gathered in Task 1.2, as well as for all other data gathered and created during realization of other WPs. All data designated for upload are verified, analysed and stored in the GIS-linked, structured geodatabase for future use (result R1.3, April 2024). The geodatabase has been maintained and kept updated by incoming, newly acquired data for the whole course of the project and serving as the main project data source for all Work Packages. The geodatabase was available online for all Project Partners, respecting, at the same time, the access rights, limited in some cases by the provisions of the Non-disclosure Agreement between MND and research partners of the project.

The online environment that was set up for the distribution of the data within the project makes it possible to share spatial data with all Project Partners in a safe and user-friendly manner. A repository of the NextCloud environment structured according to access rights to specific data and further thematically, was used for all spatial and non-spatial data saved

in file system. For selected spatial GIS data, an ArcGIS Online solution is available for presenting and sharing data with all Project Partners.

Within an additional activity of Task 1.3, a digital elevation model (DEM) for the site area has been developed to be used as the basic input for WP2 for creation of the static geological model of the storage complex and utilisation in other WPs (WP6, WP8). The DEM is based on available altimetric data (planimetric coordinates with elevation data, LIDAR data) and incorporated into the project geodatabase.

For “permanent” storage and open access to datasets and maps, the Zenodo repository (a general-purpose open repository developed under the European Open AIRE programme and operated by CERN) was selected.

2.4 Data Management Plan

On Programme Operator request, a Data Management Plan (DMP) was created as an additional output of the CO₂-SPICER project. The DMP described the data and data handling procedures and workflows in the project (Fig. 2-5). The main objective of the project - preparation of a CO₂ storage pilot to an implementation-ready stage - was strongly reflected in the DMP. In particular, this has been demonstrated by the fact that the main project results (e.g. 3-dimensional models, results of numerical simulations, site development scenarios), including the corresponding datasets have been prepared for immediate re-use by the industrial Project Partner for the implementation of the pilot storage project as such.

Fig. 2-5: Schematic workflow diagram depicting the data sources and procedures of data handling within the project.

The structure of the DMP put the accent on data accessibility. Project results and datasets that are openly accessible (i.e. not covered by Non-disclosure Agreement), are (and will be) made publicly available through Zenodo repository.

The DMP was guided by the key project documents where the key principles of data collection, generation, consolidation and storage was described, as well as the basic rules for access to the most important datasets and their re-use. These documents included:

- Project application – defined Main project results, including the related datasets and the access to these results.
- Partnership Agreement – defined the ownership of and access rights to project results, which also covers the included datasets, and, in its Attachment 1, the Background that the partners make available to the project consortium, including data. Specific limitations and conditions for implementation and exploitation of the Background were specified here.
- Non-Disclosure Agreement signed between the industrial partner and project site operator MND and the research partners that defined the rules for provision and utilisation of MND proprietary site-specific data in CO2-SPICER.

List of deliverables

Main results:

TO01000 112-V3 Set of thematic maps of the CO2 Zar-3 storage site

Other results:

R1.2 Report on pedology, geology, geomorphology, climatology, conflict of interest and nature protection

R1.3 GIS-linked structured geodatabase – project repository and international open repository

Data Management Plan

3 THREE-DIMENSIONAL GEOLOGICAL MODEL OF THE STORAGE COMPLEX

The main goal of this project part (WP2) was to develop a static 3D geological model of the storage complex with particular focus on storage reservoir properties, using seismic and other geophysical data, geological interpretations and well data acquired during WP1. In addition, a larger, simplified model that includes the reservoir overburden shall be constructed to analyse the risks of fluid migration into shallow aquifers (to be analysed WP6).

The WP2 work was mainly done during year 2022 and was generally performed according to the plan, with some slight delays in reporting. During the 2023, the requirements were mainly met from the dynamic modelling team. A detailed static 3D geological model of the Zar-3 reservoir and a simplified regional 3D geological model of the area were finalised by MND (WP leader) and CGS, respectively, with contributions by the NORCE to both interpretation versions. An important activity was to finish and optimize the reservoir model in several iterations to fit the WP3 dynamic modelling group needs. Similarly, several iterations of the fracture model (result R2.4) were prepared to find the best solution for implementation of fracture intensities to the 3D static reservoir model (Fig. 3-1).

Fig. 3-1: Final 3D static geological model in broader area of the Zar-3 site.

3.1 Interpretation and modelling of the reservoir zone, overlying and underlying rocks and faults (Task 2.1)

In 2022, the geological interpretations of 3D seismic data together with the well data and their time to depth conversions were thoroughly discussed by the MND-NORCE modelling team (Fig. 3-2). The final version was used as input for construction of the 3D

static geological model in Task 2.3. Contour maps of individual stratigraphic formations were prepared to support preparation of the formal WP3 results (mainly V1 and R2.2). Minor interpretational changes were made, based on the needs of the WP3 dynamic modelling group.

Fig. 3-2: Final seismic interpretation of Zar-3 storage area displayed on cross-line 2630.

Seismic interpretation for the regional model was finalised by CGS, using the OpendTect software. Selected horizons mapped in the 3D cube included base of the Flysch Belt units, base of the Paleogene, top of the Jurassic Vranovice formation, base of the Jurassic and base of the Carboniferous (Fig. 3-3).

Fig. 3-3: 3D view of interpreted stratigraphic surfaces in time domain: base of the Flysch Belt units (A), base of the Paleogene (B), base of the Jurassic (C), base of the Carboniferous (D).

Subsequent conversion of time horizons to the depth domain was performed using average velocity maps constructed on the base of values of stratigraphic / lithostratigraphic boundaries in wells, which were refined several times during the course of the work by detailed correlation of well data. After the depth conversion, a number of manual adjustments based on well results were made and detailed depth structure maps of top surfaces and bases of all selected stratigraphic / lithostratigraphic boundaries were produced (Fig. 3-4). The final result of the geological interpretation is a series of 13 depth structure maps: base of the Flysch Belt units, top and base of the Paleogene, top and base of the Jurassic, top and base of the Mikulov formation, top and base of the Vranovice formation, top and base of the Nikolcice formation, top and base of the Carboniferous. All structure maps were also produced in a version with a detailed indication of the extent of the overlying and underlying lithostratigraphic units. The maps represent an important part of the result V1 (see details below).

Fig. 3-4: Examples of constructed structure maps: top of the Vranovice formation (A), top of the Vranovice formation with the extent of the overlying units (B), base of the Vranovice formation (C), base of the Vranovice formation with the extent of the underlying units (D).

Thickness maps (Fig. 3-5) of individual lithostratigraphic units were also produced by CGS and partly used to check the correctness of the structure maps. The set of created maps includes: thickness map of the Paleogene, thickness map of the Mikulov formation, thickness map of the Vranovice formation, thickness map of the Nikolcice formation and thickness map of the Carboniferous. Additionally, for risk assessment purposes in WP6, a combined caprock thickness map was created, including both Paleogene and the Mikulov formation.

Fig. 3-5: Examples of constructed thickness maps: thickness map of the Paleogene (left) and thickness map of the Jurassic Mikulov formation (right).

3.2 Lithofacies analysis (Task 2.2)

Analysis of lithofacial types of rocks building the Zar-3 storage complex was based on well logs and mud logs tied with seismic data, as well as on the core sample analyses.

The lithofacial model deals with the reservoir horizon and underlying and overlying seal strata. Its main purpose is to improve the input data for the reservoir dynamic modelling and CO₂ storage simulations. Good knowledge of lithofacies patterns makes it possible to interpolate and extrapolate rock types and reservoir or sealing properties to the undrilled parts of the storage site. The facial model of the Zar-3 storage site is shown as 4 layers in Figs. 3-6 to 3-9.

Fig. 3-6: 3D representation of Lower Carboniferous “flysch” or turbidite facies of the Myslejovice Fm. and dolomitic sandstone shallow marine facies of Middle Jurassic Nikolčice Fm.

Fig. 3-7: 3D representation of Upper Jurassic patch reef and carbonate bank facies of the Vranovice Fm. overlying the Nikolčice Fm.

In the Upper Jurassic, shallow sea covered the Zar-3 area, and the principal reservoir – the dolomites of the Vranovice Fm. – were deposited in patch reef and carbonate bank facies. The original limestones were dolomitized during the early diagenetic phase. Rich microscopic documentation of the rocks has been prepared in an atlas showing the details of the rock types as a supporting material for the facial model of the storage site.

Fig. 3-8: In the Upper Jurassic, the Mikulov Fm. was deposited in basinal marl facies of the upper continental slope.

Little or no evidence has been found of an erosional contact of the Vranovice Fm. and the overlying Mikulov Fm. These basinal marls with little or no dolomitization were deposited in the upper continental slope facies. In the Zar-3 storage complex the Mikulov Fm. represents the seal together with the Nesvačilka Fm. (Figs. 3-8 and 3-9).

Fig. 3-9: In the Eocene, the Nesvačilka Fm., Žarošice Mb. was deposited in submarine canyon facies with steep flanks and slumps.

Facial maps were composed for Zar-3 storage site and the adjacent area to provide basis of better understanding of the spatial distribution of the permeable and non-permeable rocks and a prediction, what will happen during and after the CO₂ storage in broader context.

3.3 Construction of the static model (Task 2.3)

The inputs from Tasks 2.1 and 2.2 were used for construction of the static reservoir model. The final model was prepared in several versions. Each model iteration (version) was carefully tested in cooperation with WP3 modelling group to get the best interconnection of the static geological model output and the real well results obtained during the oil and gas production. Finally, a 10x10 m cell density grid with vertical cells resolution of 1 m was prepared for the handover of the model data to the WP3 dynamic modelling team (Fig. 3-10). This final resolution will be coarsened in the aquifer part by the dynamic modellers to get an acceptable grid resolution for CO₂ injection simulations.

Fig. 3-10: The working area for regional simplified geological model (red polygon).

As the construction of 3D static geological model in Schlumberger Petrel software was one of the main targets of CO₂-SPICER project and it served as a direct input for the dynamic modelling of the fluids within the reservoir after the CO₂ injections starts in the area of Zar-3. This main task was divided into two subtasks as the reservoir itself with its direct overburden was prepared in Schlumberger Petrel (working area covering Zar-3 structure and its potential aquifer zone in Fig. 3-11) software and the simplified regional model not entering directly to the dynamic modelling but covering the broader project area (red polygon highlighted in Fig. 3-10) and showing the important relationships (sealing, migration pathways) between lithostratigraphical units involved in geological setting of the area. Also as the structural modelling modules in Schlumberger Petrel software are primarily targeting the reservoir model building the static reservoir model was focused mainly in modelling of the reservoir rocks present of the future CO₂ storage area of Zar-3 structure. Nevertheless the simplified model of direct overburden of Zar-3 reservoirs was incorporated in the static model to show the details of individual rock formations relationships (Fig. 3-12) within the technical limits of Schlumberger Petrel software.

During the first phase the main focus was on seismic interpretation and hydrocarbon well results. During this phase the most prominent lithostratigraphical unit surfaces were constructed and converted from time domain to depth domain (forming the reservoir and sealing rocks for the Zar-3 CO₂ storage complex) and then they served as the main input for the static reservoir model constructed in Petrel software. These results were a base for dynamic modelling of CO₂, oil, gas and water behaviour within the storage complex.

The interpretations were done partly in MND a.s. using the Petrel software by Schlumberger and partly in the CGS using the Opentect software with contribution to both interpretation versions by NORCE. The area where the model was built was chosen in the vicinity of the Zar-3 future CO₂ storage, where recently oil and gas field is being produced and operated by MND a.s. The more detailed interpretation focused directly on future CO₂ storage was then used in second phase focused on building of the static reservoir model of the Zar-3 CO₂ storage and its potential aquifer.

Fig. 3-11: The working area for reservoir model as an input for dynamic reservoir simulation (aquifer and injection zone is highlighted as a depth color surface).

Fig. 3-12: The static reservoir model of the Zar-3 future CO₂ storage in 3D view.

Fig. 3-13: Result of final seismic interpretation – 3D model of the Zar-3 reservoir with 10x10 m grid and 1 m vertical cells resolution.

A 3D grid with a grid increment of 10 m and a vertical depth range of 0 - 3000 m (TVDSS) was created in Petrel software. All surfaces from previous interpretations and mapping were added to the 3D grid and zones were created between them, representing geological / stratigraphic units (Fig. 3-13).

3.4 Fracture analysis and modelling (Task 2.4)

Construction of the detailed fracture model in the Petrel software was finalised in 2022, in cooperation of CGS and MND. The standard fracture modelling algorithm was used firstly, but as the unwieldy numbers of fractures led to impossibility to upscale them into the final grid, the simplified fracture model algorithm was implemented in the end. The lack of input data, especially core data for estimation of suitable fault apertures, led to problems with defining of correct apertures to get realistic porosities and permeabilities in the 3D domain of the Zar-3 reservoir. Finally, an alternative approach was implemented to get realistic petrophysical properties for the 3D static geological model of the reservoir, lying in the use of fracture intensities distribution calibrated to porosities and permeabilities interpreted from the well logs. Along with several iterations of distribution of standard petrophysical properties (derived from well logs; see Task 2.5), also the fracture intensities distributions in the 3D space of the Zar-3 reservoir were handed over to the WP3 dynamic modelling team. This provided the opportunity to precise the final petrophysical properties distribution in the areas where the well tests together with increased well productivities are pointing to high values of permeability. These local occurrences of high permeability zones - in case of Zar-3 as a partly fractured reservoir - cannot be covered only by calculations of petrophysical properties using the well log interpretations and need to be adjusted during the history match process. The fracture modelling workflow is illustrated in Fig. 3-14.

Fig. 3-14: Fracture modelling workflow showing fracture intensities upscaled to the model grid: a) FMS fractures on wells color-coded by the fracture system; b) fracture intensities upscaled into the model grid; c) fractures generated using a stochastic model based on FMS data; d) example of the first fracture system intensities distributed into the whole grid based on its statistical characteristics; e) fracture model where the coverage of the whole grid was achieved by increased size of fractures; f) fracture model based on fracture intensities distributed over the whole grid.

3.5 Distribution of petrophysical properties and fluids (Task 2.5)

Distribution of petrophysical properties

After the upscale of all available well logs within the model grid the distribution of porosity and permeability in the final model grid from Task 2.3 was done. Since the static model deals mostly with the carbonate type of reservoir in a relatively large area with only locally denser dataset, the Gaussian sequential simulation was chosen as the most suitable property distribution method. It is a stochastic method based on kriging but capable of capturing extreme values in a heterogeneous reservoir. The properties should honour the well results, histogram and variogram with same variability image over the model. Firstly, variograms and variogram maps were constructed and anisotropy was tested for the dataset that was upscaled from values calculated from well logs. Several major direction azimuths were tested in the variograms, ranging from 0 to 35 degrees. Anisotropy range was tested

with values from 250 m to 2500 m in major direction and 150 m to 2500 m in minor direction, using the spherical variogram. Finally, as the only denser part of the dataset is concentrated in the segment covering just the direct vicinity of the Zar-3 CO₂ storage and the data in the rest of the aquifer are rather scarce, the isotropic distribution with the anisotropy range 1250 m in both directions was used for both reservoir zones. Final iterations used horizontal grid density of 10x10 m with either 1 m layer thickness following the base of the reservoir zone, or 1 m layer thickness with horizontal layering. All different distributions were also gradually tested by reservoir engineers to match the known volume of hydrocarbons and to match the production results in the discrete parts of the grid penetrated by the production wells. In the end, the 10 x10 m grid with follow-base layering was chosen as working option, with the supplementary option using 10 x10 m grid with horizontal layering (Fig. 3-15).

During intensive cooperation with WP3 (Dynamic modelling) team during 2023 the tens of additional distribution iterations were prepared as the initial layering and petrophysical properties distribution were not giving adequate responses of dynamic model behaviour. The rescale of original property model with follow base layering was prepared and used for recalculation to sub-horizontal grid geometry (Fig. 3-16). Also the tens of additional petrophysical properties distributions were calculated using krigging and gaussian random simulation algorithms to match the problematic history matching process of WP3 in the areas of discrete Zar-3 wells (Fig. 3-17). Finally the gaussian random simulation was used for dynamic modelling with 45° rotation, 1425 m major and 700 m minor search variogram cone distances with nugget 0,05.

Fig. 3-15: 3D model with porosity distribution using sub-horizontal layering, 10x10 m grid and 1 m thickness of layers.

Fig. 3-16: 3D model with permeability distribution recalculation using follow base layering recalculated to sub-horizontal layering cells, 10x10 m grid and 1 m thickness of layers.

Fig. 3-17: 3D model petrophysical properties distribution iterations examples. Krigging algorithm iterations in the left part of figure, Gaussian random simulation algorithm iterations in the right part of this figure

Maps of initial and current contacts of fluids in the reservoir

After detailed interpretation of 3D seismic, construction of surfaces of key horizons (Task 2.1), construction of the static reservoir model (Task 2.3) and petrophysical properties distribution (Task 2.5) in Petrel software, the next step in WP3 workflow was the construction of maps of original and recent fluid contacts. The tops of the reservoir formation within the final model grid served as the main input for the map construction. The original depths of the contacts of oil, gas and water were derived from the well log

interpretation reports by Hrubý (2004 and 2011¹). The recent contact levels (Fig. 3-18) were derived from interpretation of recent neutron logs from the ZA3 well.

Fig. 3-18: Zar-3 oil and gas field. Depth map of Vranovice Fm. top with recent (2022) position of gas, oil and water zones.

Vertical temperature model

The vertical temperature model was built by CGS as a part of the static geometric model of the storage complex and serves as an input for the dynamic modelling in WP3.

Reservoir temperature in the Vranovice Fm. measured by the downhole thermometer in the ZA3 well ranges from 50.2 to 54.0 °C at depths from 1615 to 1800 m (measured from the surface). The calculated geothermal gradient ranges from 21.2 to 24.7 mK.m⁻¹. The values are notably lower than the average global geothermal gradient 33 mK.m⁻¹. The average annual surface (neutral zone) temperature ranges from 8 to 9 °C and represents the starting temperature value. Simplified vertical temperature model of the Zar-3 site is shown in Fig. 3-19.

¹ Hrubý, J. (2004). Závěrečná zpráva. Petrofyzikální analýza ropo-plynového ložiska Žarošice. MS. MND a.s. archive, Hodonín.

Hrubý, J. (2011). Závěrečná zpráva. Dodatečné vyhodnocení vrtů Za9Ah a Za14H a MDT měření ve vrtu Za6a, ložisko Žarošice. MS. MND a.s. archive, Hodonín.

Fig. 3-19: Simplified vertical temperature model of the Zar-3 site with well trajectories, well logs and geological units building the CO₂-storage complex. The red rectangle shows the reservoir temperature and depth interval.

A thermal history model for the ZA3 well was prepared using the PetroMod software. It provides a complete depth profile of thermal conductivity and heat capacity. This may be used for further dynamic modelling of CO₂ injection associated with cooling of the rocks (WP8).

List of deliverables

Main results:

TO01000112-V1 3D geological model of the storage complex and set of structural geological maps

Other results:

R2.2 3D geometric model with interpreted surfaces and bases of selected horizons, settled wells and fault planes

R2.3 Lithofacial layer model

R2.4 Model of spatial distribution and properties of fractures

R2.5 Maps of basic petrophysical properties distribution in the storage complex

R2.6 Maps of initial and current contacts of fluids in the reservoir

R2.7 Vertical temperature model

4 DYNAMIC MODELLING AND SIMULATIONS

The main objectives of dynamic modelling and simulations (WP3) were to assemble and history match full-field reservoir model of the planned storage site, and simulate different options of CO₂ injection pilot while accounting for the most important effects related to CO₂ storage in fractured carbonate reservoirs.

The whole WP3 consisted of several tasks. 3D geological model assembled in WP2 was used as a basis for the reservoir model (Task 3.1). Task 3.2 was focusing on dynamic field data analysis providing estimates of well and reservoir parameters for the reservoir model. Task 3.3 was focusing on effects related to CO₂ flow in the reservoir in combination with integration of the results of geomechanics (WP4) and geochemistry (WP5) into the reservoir simulations in Tasks 3.4 and 3.5. This WP also provided an approach to model flow in the natural fracture network and dynamic effects related to fracture opening / closure for further integration into the history matching of the model in Task 3.4. Simulation of possible options of CO₂ injection pilot at the storage site finalized the reservoir simulation activities providing basis for studies in WP8.

4.1 Import of upgraded 3D model and upscaling (Task 3.1)

Several versions of geological model were imported into dynamic model. Sub-horizontal layering was initially used but finally dipping grid was used to more adequately accommodate uncertainties related to structure and petrophysical property distributions. Several permeability distributions were generated and upscaled in WP2. Afterwards they were imported into simulation model for testing in WP3. That iterative process was repeated several times required close and additional cooperation between the WP2 and WP3. The most suitable permeability distribution, that gave the most realistic water and/or gas production, was selected for further history matching process (see Task 3.4).

4.2 Dynamic data analysis to evaluate well-reservoir and fracture network parameters (Task 3.2)

The 20-year field production history was available for dynamic data analysis represented with different data sets including:

- Pressure and rate measurements with different sampling rates (fragmentary for some wells).
- Well tests carried for many wells, mainly in the beginning of production phase.
- Periods of well monitoring with permanent downhole gauges installed (up to 2-year monitoring period per well).

These data were interpreted using a combination of Pressure Transient Analysis (PTA), including time-lapse PTA and history matching with fit-for-purpose reservoir models using the Saphir software.

The objectives of this analysis were to:

- estimate the reservoir flow capacity, defined by the permeability times the thickness (kh , respectively) and well performance, that include skin effects and effective well length for horizontal wells.
- characterize the reservoir boundaries with mapping estimated reservoir properties (such as kh) to improve the reservoir description in the reservoir simulations.
- evaluate the impact of fractures on flow capacity (like dual porosity and permeability effects) and fracture dynamics (like pressure-sensitivity of reservoir permeability).

Many well tests including shut-ins at wellhead and downhole (using downhole shut-in tool) have been carried, mainly in the initial phase of production after drilling the wells. In addition, some production wells were monitored with permanent downhole gauges (PDG) resulting in long-term pressure measurements during multiple flowing and shut-in periods. These periods provided families of pressure transients which were analysed separately or in a combination using time-lapse PTA methods.

The results of reservoir characterization based on the dynamic data analysis may be illustrated with the reservoir flow capacity (Fig.4-1) plotted versus a NW-SE cartesian axis crossing the wells 3 and 4A (as shown in Fig. 4-2)

Fig. 4-1: Reservoir flow capacity (kh) estimated from the analysis the dynamic data obtained for different production and injection wells (ZA-3, ZA-5H, ZA-4A, ZA-9AH and ZA-7). The x-axis corresponds to NW-SE cross-section as shown in Fig. 4-2.

The following summarizes the dynamic data analysis:

- Reservoir flow capacity (kh) and well performance (skin, eff. well length for horizontal wells) were estimated for five wells.
- Reservoir characterization with kh mapping was carried out based on the results obtained for individual wells providing input for reservoir simulations.
- Dual porosity, permeability and fracture dynamics (pressure-sensitivity) effects were not univocally observed from the interpretations of the field data available.

4.3 Upscaling of geochemical, geomechanical and compositional effects (Task 3.3)

Geomechanical effects

The geomechanical studies in WP4 provided results that has been used in the simulation model. They were officially handed over from WP4 to WP3 in the beginning of 2023 (M4.1).

By analysing reservoir rock samples, using the “Coreval 700” device at VSB, the relation between pore volume, permeability and hydrostatic stress was measured.

Transmissibility and pore volume multipliers (Fig. 4-3) serves as a direct input into ROCKTAB keyword in Eclipse simulator.

Fig. 4-3: Pore volume (porosity) multiplier (a) and transmissibility (permeability) multiplier displaying the relation between pore volume, permeability and of pore pressure. The average relation from selected samples shown as solid line.

One of several possible reservoir development scenarios that was evaluated, was a gas cap depletion to 2 MPa. The idea was to generate maximal space for the injected CO₂ after gas cap has depleted. The consequence of a depletion down to 0 MPa can be seen as the shift to the grey area in Fig. 4-4. As can be seen, the stress state at depletion is within the obtained failure envelope from the geomechanical experiments that has been executed.

As such, based on the geomechanical loading/unloading experiments, there seem to be no pressure depletion limit as the geomechanical compaction strength (grey dashed line) is to the right of the grey zone, i.e., as the cores tested seemed to withstand the effective stress increase related to drawdown to 0 MPa. The cloud of data is well within the safe operation window.

There could, however, be survival bias in the core sampling program.

Fig. 4-4: Failure envelope of the reservoir samples in the Zar-3 field obtained from geomechanical strength tests. The failure envelope is displayed in deviatoric and mean effective stress. The hydrostatic failure line of 42 MPa is shown as the dashed line. The initial effective stress configuration before oil production occurs are shown in the green cloud (representing uncertainty in the pristine stress and pore pressure). A depletion of pore pressure to 2 MPa is shown as the grey cloud.

Another issue the geomechanical work was focused on was process of existing fractures re-opening and opening new fractures. As the COREVAL 700 tool enable a physical relation between pore pressure, pore volume and permeability this is only valid in the elastic regime for intact rocks. When the pore pressure exceeds the least tectonic stress (224 bars), however, fractures will re-open, and if pore pressure exceeds the least tectonic stress plus the tensile strength (267 bars) new fractures will develop. This will lead to a significantly increase the permeability as displayed in Fig. 4-5, where the estimated permeability and porosity multiplier is plotted, while calculated permeability multiplier is calculated as an exponential function of pressure.

Fig. 4-5: Porosity and permeability (without fracture opening) multipliers for the elastic regime (from Figure 3). As pore pressure exceed the threshold, the permeability multiplier for re-opening of existing fractures (titled as fracture opening) is included.

Compositional effects

A new compositional model was created for the history matching and prediction period. It should be clearly stated that the only source of PVT data so far is the PVT report prepared by INIG Krakow from 2002. The report provides a standard set of PVT experiments for the oil reservoir conducted at reservoir (52 °C) and close to standard (19 °C) conditions, however, does not address potential CO₂ interaction with reservoir fluids, as it was not relevant at a time of study. An SRK equation of state was tuned to available data and both black-oil and 8-component compositional models were created. The models showed good match for relative volumes, densities and viscosities with deviation within several percent. Different correlations were used at reservoir temperature including uncertainty to reservoir fluid parameters to estimate compositional interaction between CO₂ and reservoir fluids.

Judging by the correlation results, the minimum miscibility pressure is in the range of 153-182 bar, which is within the reservoir pressure range. A detailed CO₂ PVT study will be needed if this reservoir will be considered for CO₂-EOR.

Geochemistry effects

As CO₂ is injected into reservoirs, the near well region is exposed to proportionally huge volumes of CO₂. It is then important to evaluate that the risks of formation damages are low, e. g. by salt precipitation, hydrate formation, fines migration, bacteria activity, temperature and pressure cycling.

Hydrate formation is a function of temperature, pressure, and salinity. The hydrates form in higher pressure, lower temperature, and lower salinity environment. For expected reservoir pressures during pilot injection, relatively low salinity a CO₂ bottom hole temperature of around 15 degrees should prevent hydrate formation. With the expected low-rate injection in the pilot phase pre-heating the CO₂ at the surface and geothermal heating as it travels down the well seem to provide a safe operational regime. Hydrate

precipitation is therefore considered a very low, easy to mitigate risk and will not be a part of reservoir simulation study.

Potential salt precipitation seems to be the major risk factor for well ineffectivity during pilot CO₂ injection. Injection of dry CO₂ phase will evaporate water in water-bearing formations. The concentration of ions in the water phase will then gradually increase until maximum solubility is reached, and salt precipitation will then occur. The potential of salt precipitation depends on several parameters, e. g. water-phase composition, residual water saturation, flow rate, pressure and temperature. The risk for permeability reduction by salt precipitation depends on the location of the precipitate in the pore-space and thereby on rock properties, fluid compositions and local flow regimes.

Formation damage by salt precipitation includes three main mechanisms: salt precipitation, migration of salt crystals and accumulation of crystals at pore throats. Injection of CO₂ into aquifers of high porosity and permeability rock will give longer migration due to the injection pressure. A large dry-out zone can be formed in the near well regions of these reservoirs. The CO₂-water capillary pressure in these zones is low, and the effect of capillary pressure on salt is therefore low. Salt precipitation is often not causing much formation damage in these reservoirs.

A mechanistic simulation was carried out to study salt precipitation near the wellbore (Fig. 4-6). The reservoir salinity is 12 200 mg/l with chloride and around 26 000 mg/l if all ions are taken together. The near wellbore reservoir simulation was used to estimate the scale of salt precipitation. Maximum salt precipitation reached 10% in the cell containing the well itself. After approximately half a year of injection the salt precipitation zone stabilized, affecting in total only around 0.6 m around the wellbore. This study in combination with the literature were used as a reference for suggesting salt precipitation potential for the field in focus. The ranges for potential permeability reduction and the size of the near wellbore area affected by the salt precipitation were then assessed as: 10 - 80% and 0.5 - 5 m correspondingly. These range were further converted into well skin factor and applied in the sensitivity studies of the CO₂ injection scenarios.

Fig. 4-6: Salt precipitation in the near wellbore area (full cross-section on the left) and concentration of precipitation salt vs distance first meter from the well on the right.

4.4 History match of the upgraded reservoir model (Task 3.4)

The permeability distribution in the simulation model reported in the 2022 interim report, did not accurately match values from pressure transient analysis (PTA) (Task 3.2). As such, it was decided not to continue in the history match improvement by using the sub-horizontal grid for property distribution (porosity, permeability) but using “follow base” (i.e. dipping grid) orientation instead. The reason for the change was that using sub-horizontal grid for a dipping structure would not correctly reflect dipping continuity of the geological horizon in the reservoir. Initially, the dipping grid was used just for the property distribution and they were redistributed into the sub-horizontal grid and used in simulation for testing how good initial history match was achieved. But later it was decided using the dipping grid also as the simulation grid. The reason was the easier way of handling in the simulator when some editing was required.

The dipping grid, however, caused premature and excessive water and gas productions into the ZA3 well at the beginning of the production history that were not observed in the reality. To obtain the internal consistency between the geological observations, the production and pressure history, this entailed significant work. So, plenty of different permeability distributions, generated using various techniques and iterations in property modelling, were evaluated in WP2. The goal was to identify the most suitable one. Within the process a lot of short simulation runs (simulating a few first years of the production history) were realized in WP3. That iterative process was repeated several times required close and additional cooperation between the WP2 and WP3. The Gaussian sequential simulation was chosen as a property distribution method with anisotropic variogram distribution with the -45° rotation and 1425 m and 700 m search cone range in major and minor directions. Rather low nugget was chosen 0,05 to honour the higher variability close to the wells.

As the next step, pore volume and transmissibility multipliers obtained from the geomechanical study described in the section 4.3 were specified. The resulted first version of the full-field model was then used to condition the matrix permeability distribution to the results of the dynamic data analysis summarized in the section 4.2. The matrix permeability resulted from the geological modelling was first conditioned to the fracture density distribution (Fig. 4-7) to account for fracture distribution and then to the permeability-thickness product obtained for different wells from the dynamic data analysis (Fig. 4-1). The well-based multipliers were then inter- and extrapolated to the inter-well reservoir volumes using the moving average method available in Petrel.

The updated permeability distribution obtained via the conditioning of the fracture-density initially conditioned permeability to the well-based multipliers was tested in history matching exercises. Here, matching the well pressure history and well pressure drops were paid the main attention. Further fine tuning of the multipliers for some wells was carried out to match the well measurements. As an example, the pressure history match for the well ZA3 is shown in Fig. 4-8. This fine tuning has provided some deviations of the resulted permeability-thickness product, if compared to the dynamic data analysis in Fig. 4-1. At the same time, reasonable match of pressure history for all the wells has been achieved. For some wells, additional minor permeability adjustments were carried out to match observed gas-oil ratios and water-cuts in individual producers. As a result of the condition of the permeability distribution to the dynamic data analysis results as well as matching to the production history, the final permeability map is shown in Fig. 4-9.

The results of the history matching of the full-field reservoir model may be illustrated with the history of the ZA3 well (the discovery and the first production well in the field). Having long open-hole interval in the oil zone, the gas from the gas cap reached top part of the open hole increasing gas-oil ratio (GOR) to the level that the production from the well was terminated. Since 2006, the producer was used as an observation well allowing occasional (with retrievable gauges) measurements of static bottom hole pressure (BHP). The pressure measurements were useful in the history matching process allowing to adjust initial hydrocarbons' volumes and aquifer size and may also be used to evaluate the history matching results. The comparison of the pressure measurements (circles) and the BHP simulation results (line) displayed in Fig. 4-8 indicate reasonable matching of the measurements by the simulation results. Achieving these history matching results, the reservoir model was further used for simulation of the pilot CO₂ injection scenarios.

4.5 Design and simulations of a CO₂ injection pilot (Task 3.5)

Solvent model, a four-component extension of the ECLIPSE black-oil model, was used allowing introducing CO₂ properties as the 4th reservoir fluid (apart from gas, oil, and water). Two scenarios of CO₂ pilot injection were simulated: CO₂ injection into ZA3 well after gas cap depletion and CO₂ injection into ZA7 well before the gas cap depletion.

Legislation allows to cumulatively inject maximum 100 thousand tons of CO₂ during the pilot injection. So, focusing on the pilot itself, not on the full field application, the 2nd scenario could be implemented in the practise.

CO₂ pilot injection after gas cap depletion

It was simulated that the gas from the gas cap was produced only by ZA3 well. This well is the most suitable for the gas cap depletion due to its top-most position in the gas saturated structure. The currently open well production interval lies in the oil zone, so this was squeezed in the model and the top-most reservoir interval was opened for gas production. The gas cap depletion was terminated before water production started in the simulator due to the surface facility treating gas production is not adapted to excessive water production. The same interval as used for the gas production was then also used for the CO₂ injection in later phase of the simulation. CO₂ was simulated to be injected into the former gas zone.

Simulation shows that the field pressure declines up to 48 bars during the gas cap depletion and increases up to 80 bars during the pilot CO₂ injection, which is illustrated in Fig. 4-10.

Fig. 4-10: Field pressure during production history, gas cap depletion and pilot CO₂ injection into ZA3 well.

As gas from the gas cap was being produced, formation water moves to upper structural position so only thin gas and oil saturated zones remained in the structure, which is obvious from Fig. 4-11.

Fig. 4-11: Saturation after gas cap depletion.

CO₂ was simulated to be injected in the upper most interval of the ZA3 well. Injection of 120 tons of CO₂ per day and 70 thousand tons cumulatively during the pilot injection period within less than two years was simulated. Even at declined reservoir pressure after the gas cap depletion, the injected CO₂ has higher density than natural gas so the injected CO₂ is accumulated predominantly around the injector and below the gas saturated zone as can be seen in Fig. 4-12.

Fig. 4-12: CO₂ saturation at the end of the injection into ZA3 well.

CO₂ pilot injection before gas cap depletion

One of the main advantages of the commencing the CO₂ injection before the gas cap depletion is that the reservoir pressure remains sufficiently high to reduce the Joule–Thomson cooling effect. Another benefit here is CO₂ injected and flowing inside the reservoir in the supercritical phase.

The ZA7 well was chosen as the CO₂ injector profiting from the fact that the well is currently being used for produced water injection. The well was recently re-completed with fiberglass tubing, which makes it perfect candidate for the CO₂ injection, without significant additional costs for converting it into CO₂ injector. The nearby ZA3 well is currently used as an observation well and therefore may be further used for reservoir monitoring during the pilot CO₂ injection. The well ZA7 penetrates aquifer part of the field and CO₂ is therefore injected into the water zone.

In the simulation, the injection of 120 tons of CO₂ per day and 70 thousand tons cumulatively during the pilot injection period within less than two years (i.e. 583 days) was simulated.

Field pressure declined from initial 174 to 121 bars during the primary production. Simulation result indicates increase by 9 bars to 130 bars during the pilot injection (Fig. 4-13).

Fig. 4-13: Field pressure during production history and pilot CO₂ injection into ZA7 well.

Injected CO₂ is assumed to have lower density than formation water and oil but higher than gas in the gas cap at the reservoir pressure and temperature during the pilot. Consequently, the injected CO₂ is supposed to accumulate around the ZA7 injection well, migrate through the structure and segregate by gravity at the top of oil zone and bottom of the gas cap as illustrated in Fig. 4-14.

Fig. 4-14: CO₂ saturation at the end of pilot injection into ZA7 well.

Additional simulations were carried out to quantify uncertainty associated with possible salt precipitation in the main pilot injection scenario. Salt precipitation may cause permeability reduction in the near wellbore area of a certain radius, which can be modelled by increasing skin value in injection well. The sensitivity was run for the permeability reduced by 10 and 80% and the radius of the near wellbore area with the reduced permeability varying from 0.5 to 5 m. These ranges resulted in the skin values of 0.21 (10%, 0.5 meters, ignored further since is very close to zero), 0.46 (10%, 5 meters), 7.43 (80%, 0.5 meters), and 16.64 (80%, 5 meters). The pilot simulation described above assumed zero skin and was used as the reference case for the skin sensitivity. The skin sensitivity of the pilot injection scenario is shown in Fig. 4-15 and demonstrates about 6 bar of additional pressure drop due to skin in the most risky scenario with skin of 16.64. So presence of skin may double the bottom hole pressure (BHP) build-up during the pilot injection (achieving 148 bar), although the BHP remains far from the natural fracture opening pressure (224 bar).

As a final step, potential CO₂ injection capacity of the reservoir assuming injection at the maximum pressure of 267 bar corresponding to the induced fracturing pressure following the geomechanical evaluations for the temperature of 15 °C was estimated. Here, since the well BHP may overcome the fracture opening pressure of 224 bar, effect of fracture opening was studied applying two permeability multipliers: accounting and not accounting for the fracture opening (Fig. 4-15). In addition, the well skin sensitivity (due to the salt precipitation) was studied similarly to the simulations of the pilot injection above.

The simulation results Fig. 4-16a showed that CO₂ injection rate is significantly higher for the cases of low or no skin (0 and 0.46), since reservoir pressure in the near wellbore area is close to BHP (267 bar), which is much higher than the fracture opening pressure. This causes high pressure in the near wellbore area and opening the natural fractures. In the cases with high skin (7.43 and 16.64) high well-reservoir pressure drop is established with the pressure in the near wellbore area exceeding the fracture opening pressure only after some period of time (about half-year after the injection start for the case of skin of 7.43). This is an interesting effect of interplaying between fracture opening and skin effects that should be accounted for in further evaluations of the large-scale injection scenarios. The average reservoir pressure dynamics for the sensitivity runs is illustrated in Fig. 4-16b. The total CO₂ storage capacity in all the scenarios with the injection at induced fracturing pressure may be estimated as around 500 Million m³ or around 900 thousand tons Fig. 4-16c.

List of deliverables

Main results:

TO01000112-V2 3 Set of 3D models and maps with results of dynamic modelling of reservoir behaviour and pilot CO₂ injection

TO01000112-V12 Peer-reviewed scientific article presenting results of integrated approach to reservoir simulations of the Zar-3 field and pilot CO₂ injection

5 GEOMECHANICAL CHARACTERISTICS

The objective of geomechanical part of the project (WP4) was to characterise geomechanical properties of the storage complex and assess the influence that CO₂ injection and storage has on geomechanical properties and reservoir complex stability in order to qualify or disqualify the investigated reservoir for a CO₂ storage pilot. To evaluate potential risk, rock mechanical properties, namely the stiffness and failure strengths of the reservoir and overburden rocks was determined in rock mechanical tests. Further, the mechanical data were integrated with petrophysics, well-reservoir interactions and reservoir simulation with aim to identify the maximum attainable reservoir pressure preventing leakage.

5.1 Geomechanical parameter determination of overburden and reservoir samples (Task 4.1)

This Task's objective was to deliver data for geomechanical assessment of reservoir rocks and the caprock, which will be used to define geomechanical constraints for CO₂ injection in WP3, as defined by Milestone M4.1 (Geomechanical constraints for injection). To achieve the objective, three types of laboratory analyses were performed, i.e. non-destructive mechanical sample testing, destructive mechanical sample testing, and non-destructive thermomechanical sample testing.

Non-destructive sample testing (see Chapter 5.2, Task 4.2) was carried out using the ultrasonic apparatus that measured the travel time of elastic waves through a sample, allowing for calculation of dynamic elastic properties of tested rocks (i.e. Young's modulus, Poisson's ratio, bulk modulus). Destructive testing was performed using a mechanical press to apply a stress of prescribed geometry onto the sample until its brittle failure, determining the strength of the rock. Brazilian test generated tensile stress and the test yields the tensile strength of the tested material. Unconfined compressive strength test generated compressive stress in axial direction and yields the compressive strength upon the sample's brittle failure. Triaxial test generated stress in axial direction while the sample was being confined by stress in radial direction, yielding shear strength of the tested sample at given confining pressure.

Geomechanical tests mentioned above require certain shape, dimensions, and aspect ratio of a test specimen from a rock sample under investigation. A set of rock samples representing the Zar-3 field with required qualities were hand-picked at the MND core repository at Lužice and delivered by MND to VSB labs. A sufficient number of samples representing the reservoir rock, i.e. the Vranovice Fm. carbonates, could be selected for geomechanical tests.

Petrophysical evaluation

Petrophysical evaluation of the reservoir complex rocks consisted of measurements of sample's matrix porosity, permeability, and pore volume compressibility. There were 17 samples evaluated in total (Fig. 5-1)

Fig. 5-1: Frequency of lithostratigraphical units in the petrophysical evaluation of the Zar-3 field.

Petrophysical evaluation was using porosity and permeability of the formation to determine hydraulic units and overall reservoir quality of different formations and intervals (Tiad et Donaldson 2012). There were three distinct zones identified through the reservoir formation (Vranovice Fm., Kurdějov Fm., and Nikolčice Mb.) displaying different petrophysical properties, i.e. zone 1 being approximately down to the 1750 m total vertical depth (TVD), zone 2 ranging from 1750 to 1800 m TVD, and zone 3 over the 1800 m TVD. Zone 1 and 3 display similar relative reservoir quality, however the zone 2 displays overall higher reservoir quality (Fig. 5-2). The sonic logs delivered by MND, a.s. for the project benefit support the zonation by manifesting increased travel times in depth intervals corresponding to the zone 2 samples (Fig. 5-3).

Pore compressibility as an important parameter used in the reservoir flow simulators also show some dependence on the hydraulic unit zonation vs a function of its stiffness (Fig. 5-4).

Fig. 5-2: Reservoir quality for hydraulic zone determination.

Fig. 5-3: ZA4A well log with the outline of the sampled interval.

Fig. 5-4: Pore compressibility as a function of sound velocity for the rocks of various identified depth intervals.

Destructive geomechanical testing

Destructive geomechanical testing programme consisted of three different types of experimental tests evaluating the strength of the rock in different loading modes, namely tensile strength test (TS), unconfined compressive strength test (UCS), and the triaxial test (TA). There were 37 samples tested in total, 4 samples representing Kurdějov Fm., 16 samples representing Vranovice Fm., 6 samples of Žarošice Fm., 8 samples of Myslejovice Fm., and 3 samples of Mikulov Fm. (Tab. 5-1).

Tab. 5-1: Frequency of lithostratigraphical units in the destructive geomechanical testing programme

Lithostratigraphy	TS	UCS	TA	sum lithology
Kurdejov Fm.	2	1	1	4
Vranovice Fm.	11	4	1	16
Žarošice Mb.	4	1	1	6
Myslejovice Fm.	6	1	1	8
Mikulov Fm.	1	1	1	3
sum test	24	8	5	37

The tensile strength of 12 reservoir rock samples, and 11 sealing rocks were obtained. Based on the petrophysical parameters and dynamic stiffness cross plots with mechanical strength can be obtained. Fig. 5-5a display how the observed tensile strength correlated to the dynamic Young's modulus. Typically, increasing Young's modulus increases the tensile strength, although the correlation is small compared to the trend, as the variability in tensile stress determination is significant. The tensile strength is then (Fig. 5-5b) plotted versus the observed porosity. Typically, increasing porosity reduces the tensile strength.

Fig. 5-5: Cross plot between dynamic Young's modulus and tensile strength of sealing and reservoir rocks.

The UCS tests have had a radial stress $S_3 = 0$, while TA tests were either $S_3 = 7$ or 15 MPa. The variability in the mechanical strength at failure between the samples and between the formations represented in the storage complex is significant. The 'ZA4A_c3_b3_a' sample from 1750 m depth from surface, had visible pre-existing fractures before being placed in the UCS-cell, and correspondingly it withstood an axial stress of 3.1 MPa. Despite the variability in the test results, the triaxial tests displayed a larger axial stress at failure than the UCS tests. This implies that the material behaves according to frictional laws. When plotting the principal effective stresses at failure with $S'_1 = S_1 - \alpha_B P_f$ along y -axis and $S'_3 = S_3 - \alpha_b P_f$ along x -axis for all the data, one may derive the Mohr Coulomb failure line, $\tau = C + \mu \sigma_N$, where τ is the shear force and σ_N is the projected shear stress and normal stress of a plane at any rotation between the principal directions (Fig. 5-6).

Fig. 5-6: Axial effective stress (S'_1) plotted against the radial stress at failure for all UCS and triaxial strength tests, for the reservoir samples in a) and sealing samples in b). In a) and b), the straight best fit to the reservoir and seal samples are shown as solid and dashed line, respectively. The Mohr Coulomb failure envelope of the sealing rocks are also displayed in a).

5.2 Non-destructive determination of mechanical changes for samples exposed to CO₂ (Task 4.2)

Non-destructive geomechanical testing programme consisted of sound velocity determination and thermal expansion coefficient. These tests did not destroy the rock samples. There were 69 samples tested in total (Fig. 5-7). The corresponding measurements of the primary and secondary/shear wave velocities were used to determine the dynamic elastic Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio.

Part of the results is shown in Fig. 5-8 where the relation between the estimated dynamic Young's modulus and measured porosity is displayed (porosity was only

measured on 15 of these samples.). The Reuss lower bound² was fitted to the data (orange line). This orange curve was extrapolated to 10 % porosity and the stiffness at this value yielded 6.25 GPa (green line).

Fig. 5-7: Frequency of lithostratigraphical units in the non-destructive geomechanical testing of the Zar-3 rocks.

² Reuss lower bound for rock stiffness (K_{fr}) as function of porosity (ϕ) is given by $\frac{1}{K_{fr}} = \frac{\phi}{K_f} + \frac{1-\phi}{K_s}$, where K_f is the fluid stiffness (water), and K_s is the solid/mineral stiffness. The porosity was allowed to vary between 1% and 35% (i.e. at 1% K_s was used and at 45% porosity K_f was used).

Fig. 5-8: Derived Young's modulus from measurements of v_s and v_p on the rock samples.

The data sets acquired in Tasks 4.1 and 4.2 were used to determine correlations between the dynamic stiffnesses and corresponding rock mechanical strengths. Thus, measurement pairs of dynamic Young's modulus and strengths on the exactly same samples could be used to establish correlations. The dynamic Young's modulus correlated with tensile strength is displayed in Fig. 5-9, Young's modulus and UCS in Fig. 5-10 and axial stress at failure (s_1) for triaxial tests in Fig. 5-11.

Fig. 5-9: Correlation between tensile strength (T_0) of all tested samples and the associated dynamic Young's modulus estimated from ultrasonic measurements of v_p and v_s . Reservoir rock samples are plotted in blue circles and seals in orange. Reducing Young's modulus by 34% reduces T_0 by 11%. Seals are stronger than reservoir rocks.

Fig. 5-10: Correlation between results of unconfined compressive strength (UCS) measurements and the dynamic Young’s modulus estimated from ultrasonic measurements. The arrow shows the reduction in stiffness caused by exposure of the rock to CO₂ (reduction to 66% of the value before exposure to CO₂ leads to a corresponding reduction in UCS). Reservoir rocks are displayed in blue circles, while the seals in orange.

Fig. 5-11: Correlation between ultrasonic dynamic stiffness (Young’s modulus) and measured axial principal strength in triaxial tests. The side stress was kept at 7 MPa and the sample was loaded axially to failure; the stress s_1 is plotted along y-axis. The arrow shows the reduction in the elastic modulus caused by exposure of the rock to CO₂ (reduction to 66% of the initial value leads to a corresponding reduction in the value of s_1).

How does exposure of CO₂ lead to strength changes? The laboratory strength tests destroy each sample. As such, there is no direct way to determine experimentally how prolonged exposure to CO₂ at in-situ conditions leads to strength changes. Due to this, to get insights into the geomechanical changes by geochemical alterations, we estimated dynamic stiffnesses from ultrasonic stiffness measurements (non-destructive) before and after each sample was exposed to CO₂ in reaction chambers for six months at in-situ conditions. Five samples were tested before and after CO₂ exposure (see Tab. 5-2).

Tab. 5-2: Dynamic elastic modulus from sound velocity before and after 6 months of CO₂ exposure. For the three samples from the Za-3 reservoir, the Young's modulus decreased to 53, 56 and 90% (average 66%) of values before exposure

Sample ID	Age	Lithostratigraphy	Type	Before				After CO ₂ exposure				Change
				Vp, km/s	Vs, km/s	nu, 1	E, GPa	Vp, km/s	Vs, km/s	nu, 1	E, GPa	Youngs mod.
UH11_c4_b3_d	Upper Jurassic	Vranovice Fm. - nearby field	Reservoir - possible analogue	6.67	2.28	0.43	32.71	6.09	2.87	0.36	49.23	151 %
ZA3_c1_b3_a	Paleogene	Žarošice Mb.	Seal	5.68	3.31	0.24	59.83	5.69	2.92	0.32	49.53	83 %
ZA6A_c1_b4_c	Upper Jurassic	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	4.79	2.45	0.32	41.22	3.35	1.80	0.30	21.77	53 %
ZA4A_c3_b3_c	Upper Jurassic	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	2.11	0.82	0.41	4.93	1.86	0.61	0.44	2.77	56 %
ZA4A_c4_b2_b	Upper Jurassic	Vranovice Fm. (Nikolčice Fm.)	Reservoir	3.14	1.64	0.31	17.70	2.65	1.63	0.19	15.93	90 %

In the three reservoir samples where CO₂ and brine could react also inside each sample (not subject to control by the transport of reactive elements), an average reduction in Young's modulus to 66% of the value before exposure was observed. We used the correlations in Figs. 5-9 to 5-11 (black arrows) to quantify how this reduction by 34% in Young's modulus corresponds to strength changes. Our estimates suggest the tensile strength is reduced by 11% (i.e. to 89% of its value before exposure), UCS is reduced by 39 % (61 % of the original value), and the principal stress from the tri-axial test is reduced by 24% (76% of the value before).

5.3 Field stress and strength determination at in-situ conditions, and the effect of cooling (Task 4.3)

Main objective of the Task is to identify the safe CO₂ injection pressures during repressurization and cooling. Increased pore pressure reduces the effective stresses, and cooling by the injection of cold CO₂ leads to thermal contraction that causes side stress reduction since the lateral size of the reservoir remains constant at depth. The combined effect of effective stress changes in the cooled and re-pressured state, and mechanical strength alterations is included in Mohr Coulomb plots.

The tectonic stresses in the reservoir complex were not measured directly in the field. Therefore, to evaluate mechanical stability, our estimates of stresses relied on the application of three methods:

- Extrapolation from nearby fields
- Break out analysis

- Calculation of vertical stress from density logs (weight of overburden) and determination of side stress via Poisson's ratio (measured)

The stresses were evaluated at 1750 m depths from surface, since this is the average TVDS for the reservoir samples exposed to UCS and triaxial tests in Tab. 5-1.

The three principal stresses have been determined in the Upper Silesian Basin in several coal mines at depths from 750 to 950 m from surface in a (Staš, Kolcun, Simkovicova, & Soucek, 2003). A straight line was fitted to the data. There is uncertainty related to the observed fit, so that the S_1 and S_3 -value is reported with error bars. This uncertainty is projected to the depth of investigation. The slope in total stress versus depth (in km) is given by 24.44 ± 0.6 MPa/km and 17.5 ± 3.5 MPa/km, and the intercept of y -axis at 0.2 ± 0.5 MPa and -3 ± 6 MPa, for S_1 and S_3 , respectively. Given the average, highest and lowest fits, the extrapolated stresses at 1750 m depth are shown in Tab. 5-3.

Tab. 5-3: Variation in largest and least total (tectonic) stress based on extrapolation, break-out analysis, and lithostatic weight and uniaxial strain assumption

Extrapolation		Weight and uniaxial strain				Break out
S_1	S_3	ρ_{avg}	S_1	ν	S_3	S_3
MPa	MPa	g/cm ³	MPa	1	MPa	MPa
42.9	23.5	2.35	40.4	0.32	19.0	
				0.39	25.8	
44.6	25.4	2.45	42.1	0.32	19.8	30
				0.39	26.9	
41.3	21.5	2.25	38.7	0.32	18.2	22
				0.39	24.7	

At the same time, the vertical stress can be determined from the weight of the overburden via $S_1 = \rho_{avg}gh$ where ρ_{avg} is the average density expected to range from 2.25 to 2.45 g/cm³ (Tab. 5-3). Moreover, in weight-controlled systems, where the side walls of the reservoir are held on the side (i.e., uniaxial strain assumption), one may estimate the side stress via the Poisson's ratio via $S_3 = S_1\nu/(1 - \nu)$. Using Poisson's ratio of 0.35 ± 0.02 of the Vranovice reservoir formation the associated upper and lower values of S_3 was obtained.

Thus, based on the uncertainty in the method, the principal stresses at 1750 m depth were expected to be within the range of $S_1 \in (38.7, 44.6)$ and $S_3 \in (18.2, 26.9)$ MPa. The stresses were converted to effective stresses with a Biot's coefficient of 0.85 and pore pressure of 17.5 MPa via $S'_i = S_i - \alpha_B P_f$. The Mohr effective stress circles at 1750 m depth were plotted together the failure envelope obtained from the UCS and triaxial tests. Here, the average value of $S'_1 = 41.7$ MPa and $S'_3 = 22.8$ MPa were obtained from Tab. 5-3, and the 'worst case' had the highest value of $S'_1 = 44.6$ MPa and lowest value of $S_3 = 18.2$ MPa, while the 'best case' had the lowest value of $S_1 = 38.7$ MPa and highest value of $S_3 = 26.9$ MPa from the derived population in Tab. 5-3.

Another method to constrain the magnitude of the principal stresses in the field is the stress polygon method based on Mohr-Coulomb frictional equilibrium and breakout analysis (Zoback, Mastin, & Barton, 1986). This type of analysis weights in shear, tensile and unconfined compressive strength of the rock formation, analysis of the Formation Micro scanner results (FMS), and tectonic regime that is present in the region. The FMS

results were used in this regard to indicate presence of breakouts in a well or lack thereof. Presence of breakouts indicated that stress magnitudes overcame the compressive strength of the material. Estimating the stress regime that the region is under and observing active tectonic events in the area gives another possibility to narrow down the stress magnitudes present in the subsurface if the shear strength of the rock under investigation was known. We assumed the current stress regime to be the normal faulting with vertical stress (S_v) being the largest principal stress (Bucha, Blízkovský, & Burda, 1994). During the well logging operations performed by the Zar-3 operator no indications of extensive occurrence of the breakouts was found. The principal stresses that we obtained are displayed in Fig. 5-12.

Fig. 5-12: Linear curve fitted to the measured stress data from the three coal mines in the north-eastern part of Czechia (Staš, Kolcun, Simkovicova, & Soucek, 2003). b) Display the extrapolated stresses to 1724 as diamonds, the weight of the overburden (diamond) and the corresponding side stress estimated from uniaxial strain assumption.

5.4 Uncertain input data leading to probabilistic faulting and fracturing estimate – maximal CO₂ injection pressure determination (Task 4.4)

Determining the failure envelope

The failure envelope determines the stresses where irreversible failure of the rock samples occurred during loading. These data are may be reported in different forms, e.g. S1 and S3-plots, in shear and normal stress plots, or in deviatoric stress and mean effective stress as done here. When the stresses are said to be within envelope, the deformation is more-or-less elastic and reversible without inducing permanent damage (Fjær, Holt, Horsrud, Raaen, & Risnes, 2008).

The mechanical failure envelope of reservoir rocks (squares), labelled with their true vertical depth from surface, and sealing rocks (circles) are displayed in qp -plots in Fig. 5-13. The solid line represents the best fit through the sealing rock samples. The three other lines represents a) reservoir samples where outliers are removed (dashed), b) the long-dashed line represent the data from rock samples acquired at depth where reservoir stability is evaluated, and c) dotted line the sealing rock strength. The slope and intercept of the four lines in Fig. 5-13 are displayed in Tab. 5-4.

Fig. 5-13: Stresses at failure for sealing (circles) and reservoir rocks (squares) from UCS and triaxial tests. The depth from surface for each sample used for mechanical tests are displayed as data labels (for reservoirs). Three lines are drawn through three selections of reservoir samples where the solid line entails all data points, the short-dashed where outliers are removed, and the long-dashed line where only samples from 1750 and 1724 m depths were used.

Tab. 5-4: Best fit of straight line based on sampling of different parts of the strength data set that is used to draw the lines in qp -space in Fig. 5-13

	Slope	Intercept
All samples (reserv.)	1.63	4.71
Without outliers (reserv.)	1.64	6.03
1724 and 1750 m (reserv.)	0.74	22.53
Seals	1.73	7.30

Monte-Carlo simulation

In qp -space, the Earth stresses are displayed as dots. The position of these dots in relation to the failure envelope is used to analyse mechanical stability. Since the reservoir rocks are weaker than the seals, it is sufficient to analyse mechanical stability of reservoir rocks when Earth's effective stresses were varied.

In the Monte Carlo simulations, an individual parameter set was drawn from the PDFs of stresses, pressures, Biot's coefficient, and thermal-elastic constants. The pore pressure (P) and temperature (T) were systematically varied, the new effective stresses were calculated, and when compared to the failure envelope stability could be evaluated. For each pair of P and T , stability was evaluated 4 000 times. Since the evaluation was performed in qp -space, the number of stress configurations that exceeded the strength envelope could be counted.

Given the probable range in stresses, we use Monte Carlo analysis to sample from the distributions of total stresses and pore pressures in Fig. 5-14. The stability analysis is performed at 1750 m true vertical depths (TVDS) for the middle section of the reservoir.

An area is spanned in qp -space also at initial conditions since the pore pressure were between 17 and 18 MPa, temperature was 55°C and the maximal and minimal principal stresses were 41.7 ± 1.0 and 22.8 ± 1.5 MPa. Since the Biot's coefficient and thermal-elastic constants are also uncertain, the area of the attainable stresses increases further as P and T were varied.

Fig. 5-14: The Mohr-Coulomb failure envelope in qp -space based on the experimental results for intact rocks. Rock mechanical strength test results from reservoir and sealing rocks are displayed with grey and open circles, respectively. The best fit of the data are displayed as the dashed and dash-dotted lines. The reservoir rocks are weaker than the overriding sealing rock-types. The triaxial test results are displayed as solid line, while the re-opening of pre-existing cracks with surface normal parallel to σ_3 is shown as dotted line. Hydrostatic tests were performed with confining pressure up to 42 MPa and the rock-samples did not fail in compression. Thus, the safe stress-limit may be defined (shaded green area). Initial stresses are displayed as green cloud.

The impact of re-pressurization and cooling on the stresses could then be systematically estimated and its implication to mechanical stability could then be quantitatively defined.

This enables us to use the natural variability in experimental and estimated parameters to develop a transparent statistical realization of mechanical stability via shifting and re-sizing the stress ‘area’ as the temperature and pore pressure is varied. When the stress field (the stress ‘area’) exceeds the failure line, the stress-state is deemed unstable. By counting the number of instable realizations, the probability of failure can be calculated as pore pressure increase governs the value of p (moving the cloud of data to the left) and thermal contraction by cooling reduces the value of s_3 so leading to p is reduced and q is increased. In all, the cloud of stress-data expands and shifts towards the failure line.

Evaluating the safe operating envelope for CO₂ injection

Geomechanical stability is determined when comparing Earth stresses to the mechanical strengths at invariant stresses. qp -plots are used since in this case each stress configuration is represented as a point and we can calculate the number of points, when sampled from a series of probability distributions 10 000 times, exceed the failure line. Given the uncertainty in input data, the stress-level are shown as a cloud in Fig. 5-15. When the pore pressure increases, this reduces the value of p so that the reservoir stresses are shifted leftwards towards the failure line. Further, the cooling reduces the value of s_3 thereby increasing the value of q and reducing further the value of p . As such, cooling shifts the cloud of data both upward and leftward in qp -space. In the realization variation in a) thermal-elastic stiffness parameters, b) Biot's coefficient, c) the pore pressure and d) principal stresses are allowed, and stability is evaluated 10 000 times. At each pressure and temperature, the probability of failure is evaluated, as pore pressure and temperature are systematically varied.

Fig. 5-15 displays the visual representation of the stresses in conjunction with the rock strengths. The individual impact of cooling and pressure is shown in orange and yellow, respectively. The combined effect of cooling and re-pressurization (grey squares) enable calculation of failure probability based on a counting of the number of unstable stress situations. In the concrete example displayed in Fig. 5-15, the failure probability was 38.9% when the pore pressure was increased to 23.2 MPa and temperature was reduced from current temperature 52°C up to 27°C.

Fig. 5-15: Variability in tectonic stresses, pore pressure, thermo-elastic coupling coefficient and Biot's coefficient is included to determine the distribution in stresses. Green cloud display initial stresses (at 52°C and 7.2 MPa), while the yellow display the impact of re-pressurization to 22.2 MPa only, the orange triangles display the impact of cooling only, and the grey squares display the impact of the combined effect. Failure line obtained from the strength measurements of all Vranovice carbonate reservoir samples.

List of deliverables

Main results:

TO01000112-V11 3 Peer-reviewed article “Study of Mechanical-Elastic Parameters of Reservoir Rocks with Respect to the Purpose of Permanent CO₂ Storage”

Other results:

R4.2 3D Report on geomechanical data to be stored in the project Geodatabase

R4.3 Report describing development of stresses magnitude and strengths in different cases (side stress by cooling and modifications in strengths by CO₂)

R4.4 Peer-reviewed article - geomechanical testing

R4.5 Peer-reviewed article - CO₂ injection influence on stability of reservoir rocks

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6 GEOCHEMISTRY OF ROCKS AND FLUIDS

The main outputs of the WP5 included detailed geochemical characteristics of fluids, microbial consortia and rocks. Conclusions were made on the rock properties and possible migration of fluids in the Zar-3 storage complex. The geochemical data were further used in experiments and modelling of fluid – rock interactions.

6.1 Geochemistry of fluids (Task 5.1)

Fluids characterized in this task include oils, gases and formation waters from the Zar-3 oil and gas field as well as from the adjacent fields.

Geochemistry of oils

Based on the density, viscosity, acid values, biomarkers and other properties the Zar-3 is classified as medium sweet crude oil. Based on the chromatographic whole-oil analysis the ZA4A oil is composed of a heavily biodegraded black oil (C₁₅₊) mixed with a gasoline range light oil of very contrasting thermal maturity and alteration.

The black oil has almost no n-alkanes and the biodegradation in the reservoir reached level of 6+ on the PM scale. Black oil correlates with the Mikulov Fm. source rocks and was generated at 110-140 °C. Thermal maturity of the black oil fraction is equivalent to vitrinite reflectance of 0.86%, which occurs in source rocks at depth of ca 5 km.

Gasoline range light hydrocarbons consist of a full range of n-alkanes, branched and cyclo-alkanes, which indicate a much lower biodegradation than the black oil. Transformation ratios based on molecular composition of the gasoline range hydrocarbons in reservoir show progressive steps of biodegradation from the first “victims” removed from the mixture (n-C7) to the residual compounds (e.g. dimethylcyclopentane). Both biodegradation and water washing of the gasoline fraction is stronger in the Zar-3 oil than in the oils in the adjacent oil and gas fields.

Multivariate statistical (UPGMA) analysis was used to evaluate similarities and differences among the light hydrocarbon fractions of the studied oils. Five genetic groups (families) were identified among the gasoline fraction of the oils in the region. ZA4A oil is most similar to UH57, UH19 and NIK2A.

Gas geochemistry

The gas produced from the Zar-3 wells has in average 82-86% methane and 5.1-10.4% carbon dioxide since field opening. Based on isotopic composition the methane is purely thermogenic with no microbial contribution in Zar-3 (Fig. 6-1). Carbon dioxide originates mainly from dolomite dissolution. The ZA8AH well samples represent a different type of gas when compared with ZA4a, probably due to a long non-producing time interval and stratification of the gas column in the well.

Fig. 6-1: Zar-3 gas characteristics based on $\delta^{13}C(CH_4)$ carbon and hydrogen (deuterium) $\delta D(CH_4)$ isotopic composition of methane and $C_1/(C_2+C_3)$ dryness index of ZA3, ZA4a, ZA6, ZA8H, ZA14H and reference gas samples from the adjacent fields.

In the broader neighbourhood microbial methane occurs but at shallower depth in Jurassic (Mil-1) and Carboniferous reservoirs (Nit-1, Kro-2 and Zda-131, Fig. 6-2).

Fig. 6-2: Zar-3 gas characteristics based on $\delta^{13}C(CH_4)$ carbon isotopic composition of methane in respect to depth from ZA3, ZA4a, ZA6, ZA8H, ZA14H and reference gas samples from the Uhřice, Dambořice (Jurassic and Carboniferous reservoirs) and Klobouky, Bošovice, Hostěradky, Násedlovce fields (Paleogene reservoirs). Microbial methane is observed in shallower Jurassic (Mil-1) and Carboniferous reservoirs (Nit-1, Kro-2, Uh-9 and Zda-131).

H₂S started to occur at the annulus, probably due to introduction of sulphate reducing bacteria (SRB) into the reservoir during the reinjection of the produced water. The soil gas samples contain CO₂ in the amount 0,146 - 7.188 %_{vol}, the carbon isotopic composition $\delta^{13}\text{C-CO}_2$ ranges from -21.7 to -14.5‰.

Geochemistry of formation water

Chemical analyses of formation water samples from Zar-3 were completed in the CGS, VSB and MND labs. Complete analytical results are stored in the project geodatabase. The data serve as a basis for the CO₂–rock–water interaction experiments (Task 5.4) and modelling (Task 5.5), as well as for the reservoir modelling (WP3).

The formation water in the Zar-3 field is a typical marine, deeply buried water (brine) of Na–Cl type and is low in bicarbonate ion HCO₃⁻ content.

Formation water mineralization in the reservoir, overburden and underburden rocks

Mineralization of pore water is in general controlled by the original depositional environment and secondary alterations due to fluid–rock interactions and infiltration of descending fresh water from the surface. Mineralization expressed as total dissolved solids in water (TDS) acquired from the CGS and MND databases covering the past 30 years is shown in Figure 6-3 in respect to depth in the broader Zar-3 area of interest. Following TDS ranges are observed in the overburden caprocks (10,000–22,000 mg/L), main reservoirs (16,000–24,000 mg/L) and underlying formations (20,000–33,000 mg/L). The data suggest that the Zar-3 storage complex is a closed system. Fresh water infiltration into the overburden rocks and TDS of <5 g/L are rarely observed and are limited to depth of <1 km from the surface.

Fig. 6-3: Mineralization of formation waters (TDS) in overburden, main reservoir and underburden strata of the broader region of Zar-3 storage site.

6.2 Microbial activity in the reservoir (Task 5.2)

The DNA analysis of the water sample taken in 2021 from the production well ZA4A, depth ca. 1800 m TVDSS, was completed and 28 families of Archaea and Bacteria were identified.

Both Archaea (primitive bacteria) and Bacteria were found to be present in the Zar-3 reservoir. **Sulfur reducing Bacteria (SRB)** are absolutely dominant in the water (Desulfobacteria, Desulfobulbia, Desulfovibrionia and Spirochaetia, coupled with **oxidation of organic compounds** from the oil. Hydrogen sulfate (H₂S), pyrite and CO₂ are the products of the sulfate reduction process. The process is much more energetically favourable than **methanogenesis**, which is **rather suppressed** in Zar-3.

Clostridia, Bacilly and Proteobacteria make another functional group on the site. These anaerobic or facultative anaerobic organisms break down larger organic compound through some fermentative or respiratory processes and produce smaller organic molecules, e.g. acetates, which may serve as food for the Methanomicrobia.

Among Archaea the **Thermococci** prevail together with thermophilic or hyper-thermophilic **degraders of organic matter** (Gammaproteobacteria and Incertae Sedis) in oil and sediments. They produce smaller organic molecules, which may serve as food for methanogens (Methanomicrobia) and ammonia oxidizers. Methanomicrobia occur, however, in lower quantity. Ammonia oxidizers were also found in low numbers.

The microbiological picture of the Zar-3 site is similar to some examples described in the literature (e.g. Kotlar et al. 2011³, Kirk et al. 2016⁴), with sulfates-reducing organisms dominating the sample. Availability of sulfates is controlled by the reservoir rock and formation water geochemistry.

The probability of throat **clogging** by growth of bacterial biomass and undesirable formation of H₂S may be **suppressed** by nitrate addition to the injection water. It should be mentioned, that using chemicals, such as nitrates or bacteriocides, to fight against H₂S also suppresses methanogenesis.

6.3 Geochemistry and mineralogy of rocks (Task 5.3)

The available core samples from deep wells at the Zar-3 represent only a limited depth interval. To characterize the entire profile of the Zar-3 reservoir, 121 drill cuttings were provided by MND in December 2022 (Fig. 6-4).

³ Kotlar, H.K. et al. (2011): High coverage sequencing of DNA from microorganisms living in an oil reservoir 2.5 kilometres subsurface. *Environmental Microbiology Reports* 3(6), 674–681

⁴ Kirk, M.F. et al. (2016): Interplay between microorganisms and geochemistry in geological carbon storage. *International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control*, Vol. 47, pp. 386-395

Fig. 6-4: Core and new cutting samples for geochemical analyses. Žarošice (ZA) well numbers are shown next to each well trajectory.

In 2023, they were analysed for chemical composition using elemental analysis of organic and inorganic carbon (TOC, TIC and calculated calcite or dolomite), Rock-Eval pyrolysis, clay mineral composition by powder x-ray diffraction. The results were uploaded to project geodatabase.

The geochemical profiles in Figs. 6-5 and Fig. 6-6 based on elemental composition, total cation exchange capacity (CEC) and Rock-Eval pyrolysis show specific trends in rock properties. The overthrust Ždánice unit consists of deep water sediments, low in carbonates, intermediate in TOC and hydrogen index (HI). Menilite Fm. is exceptional in this interval with elevated carbonate minerals (probably marls of the Dynów Fm.), organic carbon and the highest HI indicating high source potential due to high algae content. Thermal maturity is low.

The Nesvačilka Fm. of Eocene age has higher calcareous component, very high TOC and elevated HI typical of coaly particles with contribution of planktonic algae. No striking change in thermal maturity is observed at the overthrust – autochthonous Paleogene boundary.

The main reservoir – Vranovice Fm. with probable Nikolčice Fm. in the lower part is built by dolomites with some clay impurities in the upper part. The formation is lean in sedimentary organic carbon. Elevated hydrogen index occurs in the lower part, most probably associated with precipitated solid bitumen from the oil impregnations.

Fig. 6-5: Carbonate content, total organic carbon (TOC), total sulphur (TS) and cation exchange capacity (CEC) in respect to true vertical depth (TVD SS) in drilling cuttings in the ZA3 well.

The underlying Myslejšovice Fm. of Carboniferous age has, with one exception, very low carbonate content, probably due to deposition below CCD. Redeposited coaly fragments make the TOC elevated, HI indicates typically humic type of kerogen. Thermal maturity is markedly higher than the rest of the profile, probably due to erosion of the upper part of Carboniferous strata. That is why the porosity and permeability of the Myslejšovice Fm. is very low.

Mineral composition of rocks

Vranovice Fm., the principal reservoir, represents an end member lithology of almost pure dolomite. The Nikolčice Fm., which underlies the Vranovice Fm., is rich in dolomite but has also quartz and minor rock-building minerals, such as feldspars.

The underlying Carboniferous Myslejšovice Fm. is composed of almost pure siliciclastic rocks (shale, siltstone and sandstone). Overlying marls of the Mikulov Fm. show broad variety of mineral composition, little or minor dolomite, abundant calcite, siliciclastics, mainly clay minerals, and pyrite. Paleogene siltstones of the Nesvačilka Fm. are rich in pyrite and have variable carbonate content. The pre-experimental results are used, among others, for optimization of the experimental conditions of the fluid – rock interactions (Task 5.4).

Fig. 6-6: Calcite or dolomite content calculated from total inorganic carbon (TIC), total organic carbon (TOC), hydrogen index (HI) and thermal maturity index (T_{max}) in respect to depth (TVD SS) in ZA3 well profile.

Optical and electron microscopy

Reservoir and caprock characteristics were complemented by microscopy in translucent and fluorescent light. Reservoir samples are represented by Vranovice Fm. and Nikolčice Fm. rocks. **Vranovice Fm.** consists of **dolostones** with fine to coarse grain size, rarely also **oolitic limestones**. **Nikolčice Fm.** is represented mainly by **sandy dolostones**. Majority of Vranovice Fm. consists of dolostones that have undergone multiple stages of dissolution (**karstification**), dolomitization, collapsing causing **brecciation** and dolomite cementation. This can be demonstrated on medium-grained dolomite breccias (therefore fully dolomitized and collapsed rock) with high **vuggy** porosity (Fig. 6-7).

Fig. 6-7: Heavily brecciated dolomite in the Vranovice Fm. cemented by fine grain dolomite and residual bitumens in plain polarized light (left) and fluorescence (right).

Caprock microscopy: Layered silty sandstones to arkoses of Carboniferous **Myslejovice Fm.** act as **bottom seal in Zar-3 storage complex**. The rock is composed of subangular grains of quartz, feldspar and rarely mica. The rock is affected by compaction (fitted and sutured contacts of grains). Feldspars are intensely altered to clay minerals or dissolved, forming modest interparticle porosity. Small compressed and elongated coal particles were observed in some sandstones. Fracture porosity is developed along stylolites. Rarely, bituminous matter impregnation was found in thin sections, exhibiting warm orange UV fluorescence.

First seal partly **overlying** the Vranovice Fm. reservoir is **Mikulov Fm.** Petrologically, the Mikulov Fm. rocks range from **marly wackestones** to (silty) carbonatic/dolomitic sandstones (Falkenstein Fm. in Austria). Overall the rocks are fine grained, with high amount of clay, subangular bioclastic detritus and (sub)rounded intraclasts and pellets. Alochems are partly leached and recrystallized, forming minor moldic porosity. Sediment is poorly sorted (bioclasts being considerably bigger than intraclasts and pellets). Bituminous matter was scarcely recorded in fracture pores.

Second seal covering both Vranovice Fm. and Mikulov Fm. is represented by **Nesvačilka Fm. – Žarošice Mb.** siltstones. The siltstones and sandstones are often dolomitic (Figs. 5-8 and 5-9). The upper part has **heterogeneous** grain size composition from tens of microns up to several mm. Besides quartz, feldspars are present together with fossils and rare glauconite. The rocks are well cemented with isopachous dolomite cement and only non-communicating integranular porosity remains. Lower part of the Nesvačilka Fm. is quite **fine grained** (below 200 μm). Pore space is filled by clay, silt and rarely carbonate cement. Large coal particles up to several cm in size were observed in some core samples.

Fig. 6-8: Dolomitic sandstone of the Nesvačilka Fm. (left) is cemented by isopachous dolomite cement with remains of interparticle porosity (right).

Fig. 6-9: Sandy siltstone, Nesvačilka Fm. abundant oil impregnation (orange fluorescence) ZA4, TVDSS 1573 m.

Reservoir and caprocks samples impregnated by blue epoxy resin were analysed using image analysis. The relative area of open pores in a selected thin section area corresponds to optical porosity. The interpreted pore size distributions suggest that in all rock types the microporosity prevails. In **reservoirs** an important contribution to the reservoir total porosity of cavernous and fracture pores with diameter ranging from 100 to 300 μm exists. The **caprocks** have about 5-10 times lower porosity than the reservoir rocks and have the majority of pores in the clay size (<5 μm) diameter (microporosity).

Bitumens in reservoir and caprocks and their correlation

Extractable organic matter in rocks (bitumens) was analysed using biomarker technologies by gas chromatography coupled with mass spectrometry (GC-MS). Selected parameters were evaluated evidencing the type of biological origin, depositional environment and thermal maturity. The same data were analysed in all sedimentary formations and oils in Zar-3 storage complex and broader vicinity. Mutual comparison was made of rocks and fluids and conclusions were drawn on fluid migration in the eastern Bohemian Massif below the West Carpathians.

The diagenetic processes and thermal maturation with depth is currently extended by numerous data from the Zar-3 broader area. The principal biomarker groups include triterpanes (hopanes), steranes and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons and their alkylated homologues (phenanthrenes). At shallow depth the parameters reflect the biological configuration. With increasing depth and temperature the molecules change to more geological form. The diagenetic and catagenetic trends of the source rocks are shown in Fig. 2.5-10 based on the deep well core samples affected by oil migration as well as those not affected. Jurassic source rocks of the Mikulov Fm. show a very similar trend of thermal maturation to the Paleogene (Těšany and Nesvačilka Fms.) ones. The $22S/(S+R)$ C₃₁ hopane ratio and $20S/(S+R)$ C₂₉ sterane ratio start at lower values in the thermally immature interval and reach the oil generation window with values of 0.5-0.6 (hopanes) and 0.45-0.55 (steranes). In the same diagrams oil samples are shown with higher hopane and sterane values of. Thermal maturity is also measured by the methylphenanthrene index MPI₂, where Jurassic and Paleogene source rocks show parallel trends with depth, the Jurassic being slightly deeper.

The general conclusion based on Fig. 6-10 is, that all the source rocks are markedly less mature than the oils down to depth of 4 km and become similar at 4-5 km and more. In the Paleogene caprock the given thermal maturity parameters indicate infiltration of the same oil as occurs in the reservoir, but the oil is not movable (producible) as it is trapped in the micropores.

Numerous caprock samples of the Nesvačilka Fm. in the Zar-3 are **impregnated** (stained) **by thermally mature bitumens**, while the rocks unaffected by oil migration, which occur further away from Zar-3, are of contrastingly lower maturity.

Multivariate statistics was applied to visualise the correlation of rock bitumens and oils in the broader Zar-3 area. Principal component analysis (PCA) of 10 biomarker ratios sensitive to depositional environment in 60 rock and 26 oil samples were identified.

Fig. 6-10: 22S/(S+R) C₃₁ hopane ratio and 20S/(S+R) C₂₉ sterane ratio in Jurassic (blue squares) and Paleogene rocks (orange crosses) and oils (green circles).

The rock bitumens and oils form 3 major genetic groups:

- Group 1 includes all oils, all reservoir samples in Zar-3 and deeper Jurassic source rocks (Mikulov Fm.). Some of the second seal (Nesvačilka Fm.) belong also to this group.
- Group 2 consists of Paleogene Nesvačilka Fm. further away from migration pathways, where no impregnations by oil occurs (Kar-1). It does not correlate with any of the oils.
- Group 3 includes Paleogene, Jurassic and Carboniferous rocks (Myslejovice Fm.), which are also not impregnated by oils and which do not correlate with any of the oils.

The interpretation is that the regional oil and gas migration in the eastern margin of the Bohemian Massif occurred since Middle Miocene, i.e. past 16 Ma. Migration took place at least 4-6 km vertically and 15-20 km horizontally below the West Carpathian fold-and-thrust belt. In this context, it is not surprising that majority of the sedimentary formations were exposed to migrating fluids. Oil & gas accumulation formed in the dolomite reservoir of the Vranovice Fm. in the Zar-3 structure. Overlying Mikulov Fm. acts as an efficient caprock. Paleogene Nesvačilka Fm. is partly impregnated by bitumens genetically related the reservoired oil but the impregnations formed by slow diffusion and the bitumens are trapped in micropores. The overlying thrust plane of the Ždánice unit together with shaly Némčice Fm. act as the third efficient seal and make even the Nesvačilka Fm. a good caprock No. 2.

The general conclusion is, that the Zar-3 storage complex is efficiently sealed and will be a **safe storage site**.

6.4 Experiments on CO₂ – rock – fluid interactions and a predictive model (Task 5.4)

The year 2023 was focused on simulating chemical processes in CO₂–rock–brine systems in a pilot CO₂ storage in the Žarosice area (South Moravia, Czech Republic).

Models involving kinetic transport through porous media and thermodynamic aspects of multiphase systems are very useful in forecasting the impact of CO₂ injections on the changes to the rock environment at the site. These models are based on information regarding petrophysical, mineralogical, and hydrogeological characteristics of porous media, hydrochemical analysis of fluid composition, pressure and temperature conditions of the reservoir, and kinetic parameters.

Data and outputs, from laboratory experiments carried out in the laboratories of the Department of Geological Engineering at VSB – Technical University of Ostrava and data received from partners within the project, were used for modelling. These were mainly mineralogical, petrographic, geochemical, and hydrogeological characteristics of reservoir and cap rocks and the composition of brine as a reaction solution.

The results of geochemical equilibrium and kinetic modelling provide the geochemical reactivity of the CO₂–water–rock system, determining the influence of CO₂ on the porosity.

Kinetic and thermodynamic models were applied using The Geochemist's Workbench (GWB) Release 6.0. The findings from the modelling are as follows. Immediately after injection, CO₂ diffuses in its supercritical form and partially dissolves in the formation water. This process significantly changes the mineralogical, hydrogeological and geochemical conditions in the reservoir. It acidifies the original brackish formation water. It changes the mineralogical composition of the reservoirs and caprocks of the storage complex. Further, it causes chemical changes in the cement plugs and behind casing cementation in the wells. All these reactions present a potential risk in the CO₂ storage process in the selected structure and can lead to CO₂ leakage from the storage to the surface.

CO₂ solubility decreases with increasing temperature and molarity of the solution, while CO₂ solubility increases with increasing pressure. In the model the dissolution was carried out until the thermodynamic equilibrium was reached and the solution was saturated with CO₂. Based on the input parameters used in the PHREEQC model (brackish water ZA4A chemistry, P_{CO₂} = 150 bar, and temperature = 53 °C), we report the theoretical acidification of brackish water ZA4A as a result of CO₂ injection and calculated chemistry. The HCO₃³⁻ ion is the dominant carbonate component in the solution at alkaline pH. When the pH drops to the acidic values, the bicarbonate ions decrease in the solution and CO₂(aq) becomes the dominant carbonate component.

The models were created in the first step for the **acidification** of the original solution at the desired CO₂ pressure ($f_{\text{CO}_2} = 70$ bar), then for the first six months of CO₂ injection into the structure and the last model for the degassing processes in reservoir and caprocks. The models are valid for a homogeneous pore medium with 100% saturation of the pore with brine solution at a constant injected amount and pT conditions in the reservoir. The injected amount of CO₂ is assumed to be 8750 t_{CO₂}/year, which corresponds to an injection rate of 0.28 kgCO₂/s.

For all rock samples, the most important chemical processes are the **dissolution of carbonates** (calcite and dolomite) and microcline due to acidification of the formation water during the injection of CO₂ into the structure. Other chemical processes that the models describe include the **precipitation of magnesite**, which replaces dissolved dolomite completely, and the formation of **secondary carbonates** as a result of the increasing pH of the formation water in the structure over a longer period of time after injection is ceased. Carbonate minerals bind CO₂ to their structure and help to stabilize the pH of the brackish water after injecting. The consequence of this process is, however, the reduction in the porosity of the reservoir rock. In the long term, these processes are desirable. The formation of secondary phases is considered useful during the relaxation period of the storage complex after CO₂ injection. The newly formed phases trap the injected CO₂ in the structure and thus contribute to the stability of the rock environment.

Experiments with rock samples in the reaction chamber also confirmed the following. Immediately after its injection, CO₂ spreads in its supercritical form and partially dissolves into the formation water. This process significantly changes mineralogical, hydrogeological, and geochemical conditions at the storage site. It acidifies the original groundwater of the brackish water type; it can influence hydrogeological parameters, especially the porosity and permeability of the deposit rock; it changes the mineralogical composition of the deposit rock and can mineralogically affect the confining layers in the overburden. All these reactions can be a potential risk for the CO₂ storage process in the selected structure. It is therefore necessary to understand the mechanism of these reactions and to quantify and evaluate them to ensure the safety and sustainability of storage.

6.5 Evaluation of changes in reservoir properties during and after CO₂ injection (Task 5.5)

Interactions of the CO₂–rock–brackish water were studied using the Geochemist's Workbench (GWB) program for Jurassic dolomite reservoir rock and Paleogene and Carboniferous caprocks. The aim was to characterize the influence of CO₂ in the geological structure on mineralogical rock changes from the potential storage site.

Models of pH and **porosity** development during and after CO₂ injection were implemented in the GWB program (Figs. 6-11 to 6-13). The input parameters were the porosity data of samples ZA4A 8%, ZA4 0.886% and UH16 1.154%, the specific resistance of the brine in the reservoir is 5Ωm, the fugacity $f_{\text{CO}_2} = 70$ bars, the original pH of the brine 7.1 and the temperature 53°C.

Fig. 6-11: Changes in pH in the formation water and reservoir porosity during the first 2 hours after CO₂ injection.

Fig. 6-12: Changes in pH in the formation water and reservoir porosity during the first 2 hours after CO₂ injection.

Fig. 6-13: Changes in pH in the formation water and reservoir porosity during the 500 years after CO₂ injection.

The model evolution of porosity in caprocks is as follows:

1. The **reservoir** porosity decreases by 1.1% during the first model period. During 6 months of injecting, the porosity stagnates and after 500 years of structure relaxation the porosity increases by 0.6%. The original value of the reservoir rock porosity was 8% and the final value after the 500 relaxation years was 7.586%.
2. The porosity of the overlying **Paleogene (Nesvačilka Fm.) caprock** slightly increases during the first model period (acidification of formation water). The porosity of Paleogene caprock during the second model step slowly decreases and after 500 years of structure relaxation the porosity decreases to the original value 0.882%.
3. The porosity of underlying **Carboniferous caprock (Myslejovice Fm.)** slightly decreases during the first model period (acidification of brackish water). The porosity of Carboniferous caprock during the second model step slowly increases and after 500 years of structure relaxation the porosity increases to the value 1.162%.

List of deliverables

Main results:

TO01000112-V9 Peer-reviewed scientific article presenting results of geochemical characterization of the Zar-3 storage site

Other results:

R5.2 Report and dataset: Chemistry of fluids

R5.3 Report and dataset: Geochemical and microbiological evidence of archea-bacterial activity, methanogenesis and pore throats clogging of the gas reservoir

R5.4 Report and dataset: Geochemistry of reservoir rocks and caprock

R5.5 Report and dataset: Laboratory experiments on water-CO₂-rock interactions, dissolution, precipitation, geochemical cementation modelling

R5.6 Peer-reviewed article on comparison of geochemical models with long time laboratory testing results

7 RISK ANALYSIS

Two main guiding documents form the foundation of the risk analysis (WP6) conducted of the Zar-3 field; ISO31000:2018 for defining the processes and structure of the risk assessment, and EU CCS Directive 2009-31-EC and its implementation - the Act 85/2012 for specific items to be addressed for long-term storage of CO₂. As per these documents, the three main steps of the assessment consist of 1) risk identification, 2) risk analysis and 3) risk evaluation, while the objectives are addressing potential leakage pathways, potential magnitude of leakage events, critical parameters affecting potential storage, secondary effects of CO₂ storage and other factors which could pose a threat to human health or the environment and includes an exposure and effects assessment.

7.1 Hazard characterisation (Task 6.1)

Risk identification

The risks considered were limited to the long-term storage phase, and were considered for a delimited geographical area, hereafter denoted “area of interest”, covering ca. 15 km² and shown in Fig. 7-1.

Fig. 7-1: Map showing the area of interest (red rectangle), with location of abandoned wellbores (labelled with well name), residential areas (white polygons) national protected area (magenta), nationally important species region (orange) and surface water (blue lines). Map generated using Google Maps.

The area of interest, which encompasses the Zar-3 site, includes possible targets at risk of exposure to a leak from the storage site, hereafter termed “risk receptors”. These are the residential regions of Žarošice, Uhřice and Archlebov with populations of 800-1100, three distinct regions classified under Czech law as sites of nationally important species, one region as nationally protected area (Natura 2000), and small surface water streams.

For this area, relating to the storage phase, the main objective of the risk identification process was to consider a multitude of possible leakage scenarios but selecting which to analyze in-depth based on importance to long-term storage integrity. In this project, a structured FEP (Features, Events, Processes) analysis was applied in combination with a review of both site-specific information and literature reviews from comparable storage sites. A general summarization of this process is shown in Fig. 7-2 as a bow-tie diagram.

Fig. 7-2: General bow-tie diagram used in to reflect main considerations of the risk identification process, covering causes, preventive and mitigating barriers and potential effects.

The FEP analysis served as a basis from which five main leakage scenarios were considered for further analysis:

- 1) leakage from abandoned wellbores,
- 2) leakage through the caprock formation,
- 3) leakage through faults/fractures,
- 4) leakage from spill point and
- 5) blowout from injection or monitoring well (during injection phase).

Leakage from abandoned wellbores is considered the most important scenario (in terms of both likelihood and consequence) and is therefore given considerably more attention than all other scenarios with respect to quantitative assessments. To the extent possible, uncertainties has been attempted quantified. Leakage scenarios listed above constitute the scope of assessed scenarios; other scenarios not listed are therefore considered of lesser relevance with respect to either likelihood of occurrence, impact, or both, in a storage integrity perspective.

The term risk receptor is used to denote humans, animals, vegetation, surface water or infrastructure that could be exposed to elevated levels of CO₂. Risk receptors that have been considered for the area of interest are shown in Tab. 7-1.

Tab. 7-1: Risk receptors for the area of interest

Type	Instances
Humans	Žarošice residential area (population: 1100)
	Uhřice residential area (population: 750)
	Archlebov residential area (population: 871)
	Site operators
Animals	Bats
	Birds
	Frogs/Toads
	Lizards
	Otter
	Bugs
	Polecat
	Butterflies
	Squirrels
Vegetation	Plants
	Flowers
	Trees
Surface water	Vápenka stream
	Zdravá voda
	Klasovsky potok
	Malénský potok
	Spálený potok [west & east]
	Trkmanka
Infrastructure	Roads
	Main/local water supply
	Storage site
	Wastewater plants (4)
	Residential areas

Relevant animal species, vegetation, and infrastructure to include have been determined based on CO₂-SPICER report R1.2 (Janderková et al., 2022) and the document *zarosice_protected_species.xls* (Vácha, 2023), which lists species under EU and/or Czech law protection and reported sightings in or around the greater area of interest.

Leakage from abandoned wellbores

The area of interest and its surrounding area contains multiple wells, including both wells currently in operation, wellbores recently abandoned, and wellbores originally abandoned decades ago. For leakage simulation purposes, only wells that are drilled into reservoir formations are considered. The leakage potential from each well was simulated using NORCE's P&A Leakage Calculator software tool, which uses a stochastic framework based on assessments of key uncertainties such as long-term reservoir pressure and size of micro-channels in the casing/cement interface of well barriers.

The CO₂ leakage potential, when assuming the existence of multiple defective barriers with micro-channels, is shown in Fig. 7-3, displaying for each well the 10th percentile, mean and 90th percentile values.

Fig. 7-3: Simulated CO₂ leakage rates for each well considered, based on assumed re-abandoned well designs and a defective barrier state.

Aggregating across all included wells, and assuming each well equally likely in terms of leakage probability, yields a probability distribution with a mean value of $1,0 \cdot 10^{-4}$ m³/s ($1,8 \cdot 10^{-4}$ kg/s) and a standard deviation of $1,0 \cdot 10^{-4}$ m³/s.

The *current* state of well barriers was judged on the basis of soil gas monitoring above the wellheads of selected active and abandoned boreholes, performed as part of WP7. The boreholes in the Zar-3 pilot storage site were, based on the soil gas monitoring campaign, regarded as currently well sealed with no leakage indications. As the methane concentration in soil gas was negligible, no methane gas flux measurement and calculation were possible.

Leakage through caprock

The leakage magnitude, based on core samples of caprock permeability and thickness maps for Mikulov and Paleogene formations, are believed to be several orders of magnitude lower than leakage from abandoned wellbores.

Data shows that the overburden rocks are much stronger than the reservoir (both tensile strength, frictional coefficient and cohesion). The ‘effective’ stresses in the overburden, with nearly zero porosity and sub-nanoscale permeability, will not be affected by any pore pressure variation in the reservoir. The injected CO₂ amounts are inadequate to reduce the temperature in the overburden, and rock-fluid interactions in the overburden are limited by the transport of any potentially chemically reactive elements due to its negligible permeability

The only failure scenario of the overburden is if reservoir ballooning/swelling reduces side stress of the overburden rock until they become negative, then vertically oriented hydraulic fractures will grow if the extensive stress exceeds the tensile strength. This scenario is deemed very unlikely, also since no reservoir subsidence nor overburden compaction effects have been observed during the production phase of the field. Based on Monte Carlo simulations of geomechanical failure, described in detail in Report R4.3, safe re-pressurization is in the region of 19-20 MPa, or higher (21-22 MPa), depending on assumed state of formations

Leakage through faults

The nearest fault identified is located in the aquifer at large distance from the hydrocarbon field. CO₂ injection is planned to be carried out in the field area and impact of the pilot injection addressed in this project on overall pressure build-up in the aquifer is assumed to be limited, however the effect of the pressure build-up and fault leakage potential should be further evaluated.

Leakage from spill points

In the case of leakage of stored CO₂ through a spill-point, the most likely migration paths are either northwest to the well UH11 area or east to northeast to the well area UH5, or in both directions, depending on the isolation degree of the reservoir body from its surroundings. Impact of this leakage scenario thus constitutes a sub-set of leakage from abandoned wellbores.

7.2 Exposure assessment (Task 6.2)

The possibility of risk receptors being exposed to elevated CO₂ levels was assessed using probability distributions of CO₂ leakage rates from abandoned wellbores as a basis for possible magnitudes. Combining this with a Gaussian plume dispersion model and local meteorological data for the area of interest, simulations of ground level CO₂ concentrations were established. Two particular dispersion scenarios are shown in Fig. 7-4, from wells UH9 and UH10, for an average (mean) case and for a (relative to mean) larger release scenario (90th percentile case). When considering an event as in the latter scenario and the distance to the nearest residential area, the maximum simulated ground level concentrations of CO₂ are in the region of 50-110 ppm (4 times less than ambient CO₂ levels in air).

Fig. 7-4: Simulated CO₂ dispersion from UH9 (northwest) and UH10 (south). Green polygons represent region where a) mean, and b) 90th percentile, CO₂ concentration levels are below a threshold of 400 ppm (ca. ambient air levels of CO₂), respectively. White polygons represent residential areas. Red line is area of interest. Yellow polygon in b) represents region where CO₂ concentration levels exceed 5000 ppm. Picture generated using Google Maps.

The polygons surrounding the abandoned wellbores represent CO₂ concentrations levels where green = [0-5000 ppm] (yellow = [5000-50000 ppm] and red \geq 50000 ppm are not visible due to no simulations yielding such ranges). Exposure to CO₂ levels exceeding 5000 ppm would on this basis only be conceivable in the immediate surrounding of a leaking abandoned wellbore, combined with gas becoming trapped in a confined space. Furthermore, there no simulated scenarios where the specially protected areas are exposed

to elevated levels of CO₂. Based on sampling from all abandoned wells, the CO₂ concentration versus distance from release point is shown within the 10th and 90th percentiles in Fig. 7-5.

Fig. 7-5: Simulated CO₂ concentration range (P10-P90 values) across all abandoned wellbores, for increasing distance from point of release. Concentration values are net contribution from release and do not include ambient levels.

7.3 Effects assessment (Task 6.3)

Exposure threshold levels for various types of risk receptors were reviewed based on literature studies for CO₂, shown in Fig. 7-6.

Fig. 7-6: Selected published air (indoor) CO₂ concentration levels and possible effects (denoted in legend) on humans, animals and plants, compiled based on available literature.

For humans (and most animals), CO₂ concentration levels at < 5000 ppm would yield low health impacts, < 50 000 ppm would yield moderate effects and > 80 000 ppm serious effects. Plants generally have higher threshold levels. Based on the dispersion simulations, proximities of risk receptors and local conditions, net CO₂ concentration contributions from the most likely leakage scenarios, from abandoned wellbores, is in the region of 5 000 ppm. This would occur only very close to point of release (< 10 m) and for site operators (not residential areas). To pose a risk to health would require gas becoming trapped/confined and presence of receptors at particular location over prolonged duration. The probability of occurrence for leakage from an abandoned wellbore is believed to be in the region of 10⁻³-10⁻⁴ in a long-term perspective.

7.4 Risk characterisation (Task 6.4)

Overview of risk characterisation and evaluation of risk matrix are shown in Tabs. 7-2 and 7-3.

The work performed in tasks 6.1-6.3 were presented in a holistic manner to reflect overall findings from the risk assessment. This involved assessments of likelihood of occurrence for different long- and short-term leakage scenarios, mapping likelihoods and potential consequences in a risk matrix, proposing risk-reducing (both preventive and mitigating) measures, and highlighting the main uncertainties of the assessment.

Within Task 6.4, the final Risk assessment report (main result V4) covering all work of WP6 has been prepared.

Tab. 7-2: Judgment of leakage scenarios in terms of overall risk

Leakage scenario [source]	Potential CO ₂ /CH ₄ leakage rate [m ³ /s]	Risk receptor group	Potential CO ₂ /CH ₄ exposure level [ppm]	Judgment of impact
1.1/1.2 Along abandoned wellbores	10 ⁻⁷ – 10 ⁻⁴ 10 ⁻⁷ – 10 ⁻³	Humans (residents/site operators)	0*/~2000 ~1700/~5000	Very low impact. Would require gas becoming trapped/confined and presence of receptors at particular location over prolonged duration, judged as very unlikely to occur. The same is true concerning exposure to operators at storage site though likely closer proximity to release point depending on location of site.
		Animals (protected)	0*/0*	Very low impact. Simulated CO ₂ concentration does not intersect specially protected areas. This does obviously not exclude possibility of exposure to singular/plural instances, but prolonged exposure would have to occur in close proximity to well.
		Animals (other)	~50/~150	Low impact. Possible exposure levels strongly depend on both location of receptor, location of habitat, and exposure is generally less likely where release points are close to residential/urban areas than for more remote locations.

Leakage scenario [source]	Potential CO ₂ /CH ₄ leakage rate [m ³ /s]	Risk receptor group	Potential CO ₂ /CH ₄ exposure level [ppm]	Judgment of impact
		Vegetation (protected)	0*/0*	Very low impact. Simulated CO ₂ concentration does not intersect specially protected areas
		Vegetation (other)	~1700/5 000	Low impact. For case of high leakage rate, vegetation in immediate surrounding would likely be impacted, but limited to distance from release point of ~10m.
		Surface water	N/A	Very low impact. Only Vápenka stream in close enough proximity to be of relevant, but release to surface unlikely to have any impact on water pH levels
		Infrastructure (site) Infrastructure (other)	~1700/5 000 0*/0*	Very low impact. Main risk stems from flammable CH ₄ accumulating due to trapping for sustained period until reaching explosive thresholds without detection.
1.2/2.2 Through caprock	10 ⁻¹³ – 10 ⁻¹⁰	All	0*/0*	Very low impact. Only relevant where migrated CO ₂ /CH ₄ would accumulate over prolonged period in soil or confined pockets, which would have a very small impact on animals/vegetation/water. No expected impact on humans/infrastructure as caprock does not intersect with residential/urban areas.
1.3/2.3 Along faults	N/A	All	0*/0*	No impact. Absence of clearly definable faults in the area of the Zar-3 structure
1.4/2.4 From spill points	10 ⁻⁶ – 10 ⁻⁵	All	~30/~150	Very low impact. Magnitude based on migration towards either UH5 or U11 followed by leakage through these well barriers. Simulated dispersion and possible exposure from these wells are, due to both leakage potential and proximity to risk receptors, considered very low.
3.1 Blowout from injection or monitoring well	~10 ⁻¹	Risk receptors beyond immediate vicinity of release	5000 – 10 000	Moderate to severe impact, strongly depending on both type of release (oil/gas/CO ₂), location and magnitude and time to kill blowout.

Tab. 7-3: Risk matrix indicating potential likelihood of occurrence and consequence, for identified leakage scenarios of the storage phase

Consequence		1 - Insignificant		2 - Minor		3 - Moderate		4 - Major		5 - Catastrophic	
		Safety	Medical treatment, minor health effects, first aid case, or less	Medical treatment with restricted duty or medium health effects	One or more lost time workday cases or significant medical treatment	Permanent disability, multiple hospitalizations, or major health effects	Fatality, Public hospitalization, or severe health effects				
Operational		0-10M USD	10-100M USD	100M-1MM USD	1-10MM USD	> 10MM USD					
Environmental		Small scale and short recovery time	Large scale and short recovery time	Short scale and long recovery time	Large scale and long recovery time	Large scale and long-lasting effect or permanent damage					
Probability											
1	Improbable	< 10 ⁻⁶									
2	Remote	10 ⁻⁶ – 10 ⁻⁴									
3	Rare	10 ⁻⁴ – 10 ⁻³									
4	Probable	10 ⁻³ – 10 ⁻¹									
5	Frequent	> 10 ⁻¹									

List of deliverables

Main results:

TO01000112-V3 Set of thematic maps of the CO2 Zar-3 storage site – joint result of WP1, WP6, WP7 and WP8

TO01000112-V4 Risk assessment report

TO01000112-V10 Report Peer-reviewed article presenting results of risk assessment of CO2 storage at the Zar-3 site

Other results:

R6.4 Well integrity logging

8 MONITORING

The main objective of Monitoring (WP7) was to prepare a storage site monitoring plan in the sense of Section 9 of the Act No. 85/2012 Sb. on the Storage of Carbon Dioxide in Natural Underground Geological Formations. All Project Partners were involved under the leadership of CGS as WP leader.

8.1 Methods and data (Task 7.1)

The main aim of Task 7.1 was to analyse internationally available tools and literature to select suitable monitoring methods for the Zar-3 site and assess their fitness for the purpose of site monitoring. Additional selection criteria were derived from the existing knowledge about the field. The research involved both surface monitoring methods and those based on well surveys (subsurface monitoring methods), with target depth ranging from the surface down to the storage site horizon level.

The assessment has covered all monitoring purposes and monitoring stages according to the valid legislation (mainly the Czech Act No. 85/2012 Sb.), specifically:

- comparison of the expected and actual behaviour of the carbon dioxide and water present in the storage site;
- identification of significant irregularities in the development of the storage site;
- determination of carbon dioxide flow;
- identification of potential leakages including their volumes;
- identification of potential undesired effects of carbon dioxide on the surrounding environment, in particular drinking water, local population or other local ecosystems;
- evaluation of remedial measure efficiency in case such measures need to be taken; and
- updates to the future compulsory short-term and long-term storage complex safety and integrity reports, including an assessment as to whether the carbon dioxide stored in the facility will be captured entirely and permanently.

The legislation defines parameters to be monitored directly, while monitoring technologies (methods, techniques) are defined indirectly as technologies that "...shall be based on best practice...". The suitability of individual monitoring methods, parameters and detection limits was evaluated using mainly the Guidance Document 2 (EC 2011, an implementation of the EU CCS Directive) and the publication "Best Practices for: Monitoring, Verification, and Accounting for Geologic Storage Projects" (US DOE Best Practices, the National Energy Technology Laboratory of the US Department of Energy, 2017).

According to both the European and US documents, the recommended general principles for the overall approach for monitoring and monitoring plans are:

- Monitoring is risk based, linked to identified risks from site characterisation and the overall risk assessment.
- Monitoring is specific to the storage site and complex.

- Monitoring is linked to preventive and corrective measures.
- Technology used is based on the best practice available at the time of design.

To find the best combination ("applicability matrix") of parameters to be monitored with suitable monitoring methods for Zar-3 site, the internationally available, "based on best practice" guideline - the on-line monitoring selection tool named "Interactive Design of Monitoring Programmes for the Geological Storage of CO₂", developed by the Greenhouse Gas Programme of the International Energy Agency (IEAGHG tool) was chosen. The result of monitoring methods selection, i.e. monitoring matrix for Zar-3 site at the beginning of CO₂ injection, based on this tool, is shown in Fig. 8-1.

Tool	Rating %	Plume	Top-Seal	Overburden	Processes	Calibrate	Detect	Quantify	Seismicity	Wellbores
3D surface seismic	64	4.0	3.0	4.0	4.0	4.0	1.0	0.0	0.0	3.0
Multicomponent surface seismic	56	3.0	3.0	3.0	4.0	3.0	0.0	0.0	2.0	2.0
Downhole pressure/temperature	50	1.0	4.0	1.0	3.0	4.0	0.0	0.0	2.0	3.0
Tracers	44	1.0	2.0	1.0	2.0	2.0	3.0	2.0	0.0	3.0
Geophysical logs	44	1.0	2.0	2.0	4.0	3.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	4.0
Deep fluid chemistry	36	1.0	2.0	2.0	3.0	3.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	2.0
2D surface seismic	31	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.0
Integrated tools: behind casing	28	0.7	1.3	0.7	2.0	2.0	0.0	0.0	1.3	2.0
Borehole seismic	28	2.0	2.0	1.0	2.0	2.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.0
Microseismic monitoring	24	1.3	2.0	0.7	0.0	0.7	0.0	0.0	2.7	1.3
Atmospheric gas concentration	20	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	2.7	2.0	0.0	2.7
Sonar bubble stream detection	19	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	2.7	1.3	0.0	2.7
Surface-atmospheric gas flux	17	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	2.0	2.0	0.0	2.0

Fig. 8-1: Matrix of monitoring tools vs. monitoring aims - results of the IEAGHG tool for the Zar-3 site at the beginning of CO₂ injection.

A literature review, looking for international practical experience with monitoring of CO₂ storage in carbonates, was used as well. Another source of input information for the study was the overview and quality assessment of existing data collected by the current Zar-3 operator and Project Partners MND. The 3D seismic data, well logs, reservoir pressure and temperature, Geoservice parameters and well tests were identified as usable sources of the "baseline" status information, with the potential to use repeated measurements for site monitoring.

As a result of the work, a list of monitoring methods suitable for Zar-3 site was prepared in form of an applicability monitoring matrix (see Tab. 8-1).

Tab. 8-1: Applicability matrix of monitoring methods for Zar-3 site (number of crosses: 5 = mandatory, 4 = strongly recommended, 3 = definitely applicable, 2 = probably applicable, no crosses = not recommended)

Group of parameters to be monitored according legislation	Operational Annex 1.2.	Environmental Annex 1.3. a)	Plume Annex 1.3. b)	Pathway Annex 1.3. c)
Wellhead pressure and temperature measurements	+++++ (mandatory)			
Wellhead flow metering & composition	+++++ (mandatory)			
Downhole pressure and temperature measurements	+++++ (mandatory)		++++	++++
Geophysical logs (well logging)		+++	++++	++++

Tracers		+++	++	+++
Surface seismic (3D, multi-component seismic)				
Deep (Downhole) fluid chemistry		++	+++	++
Borehole seismic (VSP, cross-hole)			++++	++
Microseismic monitoring			+++	+++
Atmogeochimistry		++++		
Borehole gravimetry				

For suitable seismic monitoring, special feasibility study was subcontracted. This study was based on the existing seismic data from the site and available geological and petrophysical information and combined them with forward modelling and creation of synthetic seismograms. Various seismic techniques like surface 3D, VSP (incl. 3D-VSP) or cross-hole were evaluated.

The following recommendations for seismic monitoring at Zar-3 site were concluded based on the report:

- Surface seismic monitoring of the CO₂ injection into the depleted oil and gas reservoir has limited chances of imaging the plume because of the small time-lapse signal level;
- Borehole seismic is likely to be useful in detecting and imaging the plume (because of the higher degree of repeatability); DAS receivers are the preferred option;
- A combination of offset VSPs (potentially with permanent sources) and 4D VSP are the preferred set of geometries;
- Application of cross-hole time-lapse seismic technique is feasible. However, the main motivation to use it is likely related to the imaging of the plume using reflected waves rather than travel time tomography.

To conclude, the 4D (time-lapse) VSP with offset geometry and with permanent DAS receivers were recommended for the seismic monitoring. Mainly vertical wells and/or moderately deviated wells, i.e. ZA3, ZA4A and ZA6A are planned to use. In case that new injection well would be drilled, the well ZA7 (originally considered as injection well) could be used for VSP measurement. Utilization of horizontal wells (ZA5H, ZA8AH, ZA9AH, ZA14H) for VSP was regarded as limited, mainly due to technical issues with receiver's installation.

8.2 Atmogeochimical monitoring (Task 7.2)

Atmogeochimical monitoring belongs to the group of basic monitoring methods used for all terrestrial CO₂ storage sites. The results will serve as a background for the future monitoring measurements during and after the true CO₂ storage making it possible to identify newly formed soil gas anomalies, if any. Detailed baseline monitoring above the field was performed to determine soil gas distribution, potential anomalies and to improve the knowledge of the seal efficiency based on (1) periodical and (2) continuous soil gas monitoring.

The periodical monitoring campaigns were based on 95 monitoring points (Fig. 8-2) using a portable Ecoprobe-5TM instrument (RS Dynamics) with 4 infra-red detectors with independent channels for selective analyses of carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane (CH₄), total petroleum (TP = CH₄ to C₄H₁₀) and oxygen (O₂). The soil gas composition was measured in each of monitoring point at depth interval of 10-80 cm in holes drilled by a hand-drill prior to the measurement (Fig. 8-3). To cover the different seasons of the year, the periodical monitoring took place 3 times a year from spring 2021 to summer-autumn 2023. In each of 8 monitoring campaigns, up to 10 gas samples were collected using manual pump and Tedlar bags or 40 ml EPA vials. The samples were analysed in laboratory by gas chromatography (GC-TCD-FID). Laboratory results were used for calibration of the entire set of field measurements.

For the continuous monitoring, 5 monitoring points from the periodical monitoring grid (Figs. 8-2 and Fig. 8-3) were selected. The continuous monitoring was performed from June 2021 to October 2023 using permanent probes (Sapienza University of Rome and Idogeosol company) with independent channels for CO₂ and CH₄. Hourly sampling interval was selected resulting in 24 measured values a day. The probes were buried 60-80 cm below the ground surface.

The soil gas baseline monitoring consisted of following key steps:

- Periodical field measurements 3 times a year in a grid of 95 monitoring points
- Continuous monitoring of CO₂ in soil gas at 5 monitoring points
- Cross check gas sample collection, their chromatographic lab analyses and based on that the final data correction
- Spatial analysis of the measured data using 2D contour mapping software
- Time series analysis of the continuous measurement data.

Meteorological data, such as temperature (°C), relative humidity (%) and atmospheric pressure (hPa) were measured 1.5 m above the ground level by the Comet instrument calibrated by the publicly available meteorological data of the Czech Hydrometeorological Institute at the Brno – Tuřany airport located 23.5 km to the NW.

Fig. 8-2: Soil gas monitoring grid composed of 68 (labelled 1 - 68) + 27 (labelled 101 – 127) monitoring points for periodical monitoring. Position of 5 permanent probes for continuous monitoring included.

Fig. 8-3: Field soil gas measurement above the Zar-3 oil & gas field using Ecoprobe 5™ portable instrument (RS Dynamics, left and middle), permanent probe used for continuous soil gas monitoring is on the right.

Strong variability of CO₂ content in soil gas was observed. Seasonal vegetation and microbiological activity were interpreted as the main controlling factor of CO₂ in soil gas. The highest CO₂ content was measured in summer-autumn campaigns (9.67 %_{vol} in 2021, 6.42%_{vol} in 2022 and 6.28%_{vol} in 2023) with trends of spring increase and autumn decrease. The minimum CO₂ content in soil gas – typically below 0.5%_{vol} – was measured in winter campaigns.

The rainfall total was identified as the second most important factor controlling the CO₂ content in soil gas. The 2021 and 2023 were typical by high rainfalls and higher CO₂ in soil gas, as compared to dry 2022 with lower CO₂ content in soil gas.

The land use represented third most important factor. The grasslands and forests showed much stronger difference in soil gas composition between summer and winter when compared to cultivated fields. Cultivation and mainly ploughing takes place in early spring and later autumn results in stronger devolatilization of soils. Arable fields showed in general lower sampling under-pressure indicating higher permeability of the soil profile. Our interpretation was that this is the reason why fields have markedly lower CO₂ content in soil gas when compared with grasslands and forests.

Fig. 8-4 summarizes all monitoring campaigns showing similarities in CO₂ in soil gas patterns among seasons in different years. Maps in Fig. 8-4 are ordered by years in rows and seasons in columns. For the ranges of CO₂ in soil gas, see Tab. 8-2.

Fig. 8-4: Average CO₂ content in soil gas in all 8 monitoring campaigns with comparable CO₂ in soil gas patterns highlighted.

Tab. 8-2: CO₂ (%_{vol}) in soil gas: range is given as numerator, averages as denominator; number of monitoring points in parentheses below the land use

Campaign	Land use	Field (67)	Grass (20)	Grove (8)	All (95)
1. spring 2021		<u>0.07 – 6.14</u> 1.05	<u>0.08 – 9.09</u> 2.81	<u>0.50 – 3.69</u> 2.05	<u>0.07 – 9.09</u> 1.51
2. summer-autumn 2021		<u>0.06 – 9.67</u> 2.25	<u>0.26 – 6.93</u> 3.32	<u>0.46 – 5.00</u> 2.29	<u>0.06 – 9.67</u> 2.47
3. winter 2021-2022		<u>0.07 – 2.33</u> 0.35	<u>0.09 – 0.85</u> 0.46	<u>0.07 – 1.29</u> 0.51	<u>0.07 – 2.33</u> 0.38
4. spring 2022		<u>0.09 – 3.09</u> 0.52	<u>0.12 – 5.23</u> 1.10	<u>0.18 – 2.26</u> 0.98	<u>0.09 – 5.23</u> 0.68
5. summer-autumn 2022		<u>0.12 – 2.21</u> 0.60	<u>0.18 – 6.42</u> 2.23	<u>0.32 – 2.44</u> 0.87	<u>0.12 – 6.42</u> 0.97
6. winter 2022-2023		<u>0.04 – 1.52</u> 0.18	<u>0.07 – 1.25</u> 0.41	<u>0.10 – 1.06</u> 0.38	<u>0.04 – 1.52</u> 0.25
7. spring 2023		<u>0.09 – 4.38</u> 1.07	<u>0.96 – 5.61</u> 2.27	<u>1.32 – 2.88</u> 2.25	<u>0.09 – 5.61</u> 1.42
8. summer-autumn 2023		<u>0.30 – 5.40</u> 1.28	<u>0.76 – 5.72</u> 2.31	<u>0.38 – 6.28</u> 1.82	<u>0.30 – 6.28</u> 1.54

Content of CO₂ in soil gas measured by permanent probes (Fig. 8-5) provided much more detailed data set with trend of spring increase, summer maximum, autumn decrease and winter minimum observed in periodical monitoring. The measured annual maximum CO₂ content in soil gas was up to 9 %_{vol} in summer 2021 but only up to 6 %_{vol} in 2022 and 2023 (Fig. 8-5). The differences were interpreted as a result of vegetation and microbiological activity related to the weather conditions (Fig. 8-6). Strong increase in CO₂ in soil gas corresponded to the period after strong rainfalls. All the permanent probes were placed in grasslands to exclude the potential effects of the land use and soil devolatilization. The differences among the trends measured by individual permanent probes (shown in colours in Fig. 8-5) were primarily caused by different soil types, water table level and vegetation in situ. The highest values (green line in Figs. 8-5 and 8-6) were observed in the valley floodplain with clayey low permeability on top of the soil profile. The lowest CO₂ values were observed on hilltops in more sandy soils.

Fig. 8-5: Time plot of CO₂ content in soil gas measured by permanent probes. For probe locations see Fig. 8-2. Timing of the periodical monitoring campaigns (usually 3-4 days) are marked by blue pointers.

Fig. 8-6: Time plot of CO₂ content in soil gas measured by permanent probes compared by the most important weather conditions factors – precipitation/ rainfall total, atmospheric pressure and atmospheric temperature.

No methane, nor the total petroleum anomalies were detected in soil gas above the Zar-3 oil & gas field during the baseline monitoring. The maximum CH₄ values in soil gas were < 0.5 %_{vol} and were not confirmed by repeated measurements at the same place, nor in different seasons. The methane content in soil gas of < 0.5 %_{vol} is usual, not anomalous in wet soils. It is caused by microbiological methanogenic activity and, in case of cultivated agricultural fields, may be enhanced by manure field fertilization.

To evaluate the potential leakage pathways via existing wells, the soil gas measurements of both well hubs (production platforms) of the Zar-3 oil & gas field was carried out in February 2023. The maximum measured CH₄ content was 0.6 %_{vol}. The soil gas composition was measured during the winter season, when, in general, negligible interference by biological methanogenic activity was observed. The boreholes in operation above the Zar-3 oil & gas field are regarded as tight with no leakage indications based on the soil gas monitoring campaign.

The CO₂ baseline carried out over multiple seasons made it possible to quantify the natural variability and to establish the threshold values that could indicate the potential leakage. The results of this task will serve as a background for the future monitoring measurements during and after the true CO₂ storage making it possible to identify newly formed anomalies, if any.

8.3 Seismic monitoring (Task 7.3)

Seismic monitoring is another representative of basic monitoring methods used for all CO₂ storage sites onshore. The 2011 EU Directive Implementation of Directive 2009/31/EC on the Geological Storage of Carbon Dioxide, Guidance Document 2 mentions the seismicity as one of the data for the characterization of the CO₂ storage site, while stressing the importance of knowing the seismicity for the "baseline characterization" based on known earthquake data. The need for knowledge of induced seismicity is mentioned as well.

The establishing of seismic monitoring baseline required a long-term survey due to possible changes of the local stress regime, which may potentially lead to occurrence of induced seismic events. The natural seismicity was measured from August/September 2021 to August 2023. A monitoring network consisting of 5 monitoring stations was used (Fig. 8-7). The stations were equipped with 1 second sensor LE3D and Vistec Gaia digitiser, sampling rate 250 Hz. The station operated in autonomous mode, in triggering regime, with daily status report, the data were stored on SD-card and periodically (cca 6 month) collected. The internal time was synchronised by GPS. All the system was powered from a battery charged from a solar panel. All the devices (but the antennas and solar panel) were closed in a protecting box

A two-step procedure of seismograms interpretation was used: (1) by preliminary automatic picking and (2) by manual detailed interpretation of relevant seismograms. For the purposes of induced seismicity monitoring related to the Step-Rate test, a temporal seismic network composed of 6 seismic stations was set up (Fig. 8-8).

Fig. 8-7: Map with positions of the permanent and temporal seismic monitoring networks in the Zar-3 area.

Fig. 8-8: Seismological monitoring at the Zar-3 site. Seismic monitoring station (left) powered by the solar panel (middle). Deployment of the temporal seismic network on the right.

The baseline seismological monitoring at Zar-3 is based on both Data set and report with results of seismic monitoring and Report of seismic and macroseismic observation in the vicinity of CO₂ storage site Žarošice (Jechumtálová & Kolář, 2021). Second mentioned summarized the historical events with known macroseismic effect and tectonic events which were recorded in the vicinity of the area. The estimated value of maximal acceleration in the area did not exceed 0.1 g in any case based on the data.

During the seismological monitoring in the area, no natural nor induced seismic activity was measured directly at the site (Figs. 8-9 and 8-10). On the other hand, induced

seismicity events related to the mining areas near Ostrava and Lubin (Poland) were detected (Fig. 8-10) as well as the natural seismicity related to the Carpathian system unit (e.g. from Austrian/Hungarian border or for Slovakia – Dobrá Voda) or the strong teleseismic events. All observed local events were assigned to the query blasts in the near queries. (Lom Tasovice, Kamenolom Olbramovice, Lom Dolní Kounice, Lom Želešice, Kamenolom Vícenice, Lomy cementárny Mokrá, Kamenolom Luleč, Kamenolom Lhota Rapotina, Lom Předklášteří, Lom Mirošov, Lom Ořechov, Starý kameňolom Rohozník na Záhorí, Kameňolom Trstín, Kameňolom Čachtice).

Fig. 8-9: Map with the seismic events from the period of monitoring with anthropogenic or tectonic origin labelled. No seismic activity neither at the site nor in its direct vicinity was measured.

Fig. 8-10: Map of the broader area with tectonic seismic event magnitudes.

During a Step-Rate test a temporal denser network was installed. It consisted of 11 stations equipped by ZATLAND 3C (Magseis Fairfield) independent instruments. The sampling rate was 250 Hz, and these small devices were shallowly buried in at the observation points for short time (several weeks); the instruments operate completely autonomously during the whole campaign. This denser network was designed and installed with the intention to study in dine details any activity possibly induced by the test.

The SRT at Zar-7 was carried out on December 19th, 2023. It was designed to verify the reservoir absorption capacity for 3 different modes (170, 240, 310 l/min), each for 3 hours. A total of 135 m³ of working fluid was collected in the buffer tanks prior to the test. A cementing unit MPU - 400 with pressure and flow recording capability was used for the test. The test was, however, terminated after only about 5 hours without achieving the planned (expected) results. The recording from the downhole manometer shows only a minimal increase in bearing pressure (approx. 0.15 MPa) even at the maximum liter of thrust.

During the SRT, some increased noise / very weak signal was measured by several of the closest seismic stations. It might be very weak events as well, however, the signal-to-noise ratios were very low so that hypothesis could not be verified. Therefore, no significant induced seismic was observed during the SRT.

8.4 Shallow groundwater monitoring (Task 7.4)

The shallow groundwater monitoring is essential for both understanding the shallow groundwater regime on the site and establishing a baseline for subsequent monitoring of groundwater quality in later stages of site development.

For the shallow groundwater baseline monitoring, 19 monitoring points/objects (Fig. 8-11), e.g. shallow wells, boreholes, water pumps and springs (Fig. 8-12), were selected. The shallow hydrogeological monitoring campaigns were performed in March, June, October and December to cover all seasons of the year from 2021 to 2023. In 2023, the campaigns were performed in March and October only.

Following parameters were monitored: groundwater level (m), spring yield (l/s), electrical conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$), pH (-) and water temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$). The groundwater level was measured in five boreholes and five wells using the water-level indicator cable with ca. 1 cm accuracy. Spring yield was monitored in two localities – the water flowing out of the spring was collected in a container; the time taken to fill the container was measured to calculate the yield. The water conductivity is usually reported as specific conductance, relative to the conductivity of pure water at 25 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. An EC meter capable of providing such values was used to measure water conductivity.

Fig. 8-11: Position of 19 original groundwater monitoring points near the Zar-3 site. Access to 3 monitoring points (labelled in red) was not possible in 2022 nor in 2023.

Fig. 8-12: Shallow groundwater monitoring points/objects: shallow borehole (left), spring (middle) and water pump (right).

The results of the individual measurements reflect the natural conditions in the area of interest, except for minor deviations that can be attributed to inaccuracies and errors. The water temperature (Fig. 8-13) and groundwater level (Fig. 8-14) reflect the effect of seasonal variations (temperature) and the depth of water circulation. Water with deeper circulation has more stable temperature during different season of the year (and vice versa).

Fig. 8-13: Water temperature (°C) reflecting the seasonal temperature variations in monitored objects.

Fig. 8-14: Groundwater level measurements (m) in monitored objects on the site.

The monitoring results indicate no anomalies were observed (nor in the water temperature, groundwater level, spring yield, electrical conductivity (Fig. 8-15) or pH (Fig. 8-16) in Zar-3 area as all measured data correspond to the expected natural conditions typical for wider region of the Zar-3.

Fig. 8-15: Water electrical conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) results measured in monitored objects on the Zar-3 site.

Fig. 8-16: pH (-) results measured in monitored objects on the Zar-3 site.

All the determined values were stored in the database managed by CGS. Due to the regular three-year monitoring, basic comparative values for individual parameters are available. The individual objects used for the shallow groundwater monitoring can be easily accessed and re-used in the future for possible comparative measurements. The possible impact of the CO₂ injection and storage can thus be monitored.

Hydrogeological model of groundwater flow

In order to assess potential contamination of shallow groundwater by possible CO₂ leakage, a shallow hydrogeological model of the overburden of the storage area was created by VSB.

The results of the shallow groundwater flow model are presented in the form of groundwater level contours for individual layers in 3D (Fig. 8-17) and in 2D (Fig. 8-18, Fig. 8-19).

Fig. 8-17: Shallow groundwater level contours in model domain.

Fig. 8-18: Shallow groundwater level contours in the 1st numerical layer (Quaternary).

Fig. 8-19: Groundwater level contours in the 5th numerical layer (Carpathian flysch)

One of the objectives of the modelling study was to analyse the risk of CO₂ leakage through the monitoring well. Since the software used only allows the simulation of single phase fluid flow, leakage was simulated through H⁺ ions that would be hydrochemically generated after the release of gaseous CO₂ into groundwater. The transport was simulated as advective-dispersive since reactive transport is not expected in the case of H⁺ ions.

Transport was simulated as transient in a stationary flow field, the simulation period was 20 years. Taking into account the objective of the study, a conservative scenario was chosen: a CO₂ leaky well with a constant source of H⁺ ions of 7.94.10⁻⁶ mol/L. The initial concentration and the concentration in the precipitation were given 3.16.10⁻⁸ mol/l. Transport modelling was performed in MT3DMS and particle tracking in MODPATH. The results of transport modelling in MT3DMS are presented in Fig. 8-20. It is obvious that the impact of potential leakage is based on the modelling very local.

The solute transport modelling proved the low mobility of solutes in low permeable rock environment in the model. The only vulnerable layer is Quaternary layer where the solutes are transported towards the closest drainage base – stream in the distance of 715 m. In the flysch rock mass the transport path did not exceed 180 m from the borehole.

Fig. 8-20: Transport modelling of H⁺ ions, simulation of 20 years of transport in steady state flow field, the length of plume in the first layer 715 m, in the fifth layer 180 m.

The groundwater flow and solute transport model was built and calibrated in the model domain at natural hydrological boundaries (catchment). The modelling study supports the expectation of very low permeable hydrogeological structures with low recharge. The majority of groundwater flow is located within narrow alluvial deposits and the weathered zone of the Carpathian flysch; the flow directions are consistent with the terrain.

The simulation of potential leakage from the monitoring borehole of the storage reservoir impacted only very locally the shallow zone based on the model. Thus, the potential environmental impact of leakage would be very low.

8.5 Reservoir containment monitoring (Task 7.5)

The analysis and evaluation of available dynamic field data have shown that installation of permanent downhole gauge (PDG) in production wells is an effective option for permanent well and reservoir monitoring for the fractured formation in focus. Application of time-lapse PTA in combination with fit-for-purpose reservoir simulations (Shchipanov, Berenblyum, & Kollbotn, 2014) allowed for monitoring of well and reservoir parameters. Similar monitoring approach is suggested for the planned CO₂ pilot.

A design of well monitoring system was suggested for the CO₂ injection well including installation of permanent wellhead pressure and temperature gauges in combination with flow-meter at the wellhead. This will allow to monitor the wellbore and well performance as well as evaluate changes in the near wellbore area of the reservoir, which may challenge the reservoir containment of the injected CO₂.

A step-rate well test with water injection is suggested before the CO₂ pilot to study potential opening of natural fractures at injection and reduce the uncertainty with geomechanical parameters, e.g. to evaluate unknown parameters such as minimum horizontal stress.

The feasibility study of step-rate CO₂ injection confirmed that PTA of the step-responses may be used to:

- Evaluate CO₂ plume growth in the near wellbore area.

- Detect opening of natural fractures.

Similar approach may be further tested for detection of induced fracturing, which may happen after natural fracture opening as predicted by the geomechanical evaluations. This effect may be addressed in a future study.

8.6 Site monitoring plan (Task 7.6)

According to the Act No. 85/2012 Sb. on storage of carbon dioxide in natural underground geological formations, storage site monitoring is one of the main obligations of a storage site operator, both during site operations and after site closure. Monitoring has to be based on a comprehensive monitoring plan fully satisfying the requirements of the Act.

The Site monitoring plan is one of the main obligations of a storage site operator, both during site operations and after site closure. The main goal was to (1) test the prescribed methodology for a specific geological location and, at the same time, to (2) prepare an important document for the application for a CO₂ injection permit that will need to be submitted before any CO₂ can be injected into the reservoir. The Site monitoring plan involved the international CCS project guidelines (such as the Guidance Documents to the European CCS Directive) and other international literature as an input. Other key inputs include the reports of R7.4 Applicability matrix of monitoring methods at Zar-3, R7.8 Feasibility study on applicability of seismic methods for CO₂ plume monitoring, R7.3 Data set and Technical Report on atmogeochemical monitoring results, R7.6 Data set and report with results of reservoir containment monitoring, R7.5 Data set and report with results of shallow groundwater monitoring and R7.7 Data set and report with results of seismic monitoring of the CO₂-SPICER project.

The Site monitoring plan was prepared despite the planned CO₂ to be injected into the Zar-3 storage complex is below the limit of 100,000 t and thus this pilot project is not subject to the provisions of the Act due to the given amount.

The Site monitoring plan was prepared in a way ensuring full compliance with applicable legislation as well as the recommendations set out in the Guidance Documents, including the specification of individual monitoring stages, monitoring methods and their respective scopes, parameters, survey frequencies, etc.

List of deliverables

Main results:

TO01000112-V3 Set of thematic maps of the CO₂ Zar-3 storage site – joint result of WP1, WP6, WP7 and WP8

TO01000112-V5 Site monitoring plan

Other results:

R7.3 Data set and Technical Report on atmogeochemical monitoring results

R7.4 Applicability matrix of monitoring methods at Zar-3

R7.5 Data set and report with results of shallow groundwater monitoring

R7.6 Data set and report with results of reservoir containment monitoring

R7.7 Data set and report with results of seismic monitoring

R7.8 Feasibility study on applicability of seismic methods for CO₂ plume monitoring

References

Shchipanov, A., Berenblyum, R., & Kollbotn, L. (2014). Pressure Transient Analysis as an Element of Permanent Reservoir Monitoring (SPE-170740). *SPE Annual Technical Conference and Exhibition*. Amsterdam, The Netherlands, 27-29 October. doi:10.2118/170740-MS

9 SCENARIOS OF FUTURE DEVELOPMENT

The main objective of the Work Package is to prepare future site development plans, and design surface and subsurface facilities for the selected pilot site. The work was tightly connected to WP3 by both using the simulation results prepared under WP3 but also in coordinating MND design scenarios with it.

The outcomes of WP8 are essential by both providing the first evaluation of infrastructure needed, but also the first outlook into how the future site development scenarios for the full field implementation might look like.

9.1 Value chain analysis for CO₂ supply, transport, EOR and storage (Task 8.1)

Task 8.1 completes the WP8 activities with evaluation of the CCS value chain built around Zar-3 field. Three scenarios were considered: a single point capture with transport to Zar-3 site, on-site Blue Hydrogen production and Direct Air Capture Scenarios were evaluated.

The key finding is that single point capture scenario definitely is techno-economic feasible. Blue Hydrogen one remains under question as small scale SMR plan require large upfront CAPEX investments. DAC in current state of technology and electricity emissions profile in Czechia shows too large of environmental footprint.

It is important to state that the costs and the volume of CO₂ capture are obtained using the built-in functionality of the H2020 Strategy CCUS tool without direct interactions with the facility and therefore number could be somewhat inaccurate. However, the main purpose of the exercise was to estimate the cost ranges, rather than detail the scenario.

A basecase scenario looked at CO₂ capture at Lihovar Kojetín bioethanol factory with a truck transport to Zar-3 site. Based on the estimations carried out (See R3.8 for more details) a CAPEX of 5.83M Euro and fixed and variable OPEX, respectively, at 0.87 and 0.37M Euro were estimated.

Transport was assumed to be done by leased trucks resulting in 0 CAPEX and an OPEX of 9.285 MEuro.

Storage complex, by utilizing facilities, infrastructure and well available at Zar-3 site resulted in a fairly low CAPEX of 0.12 MEuro and an OPEX of 12.44M Euro. The key scenario KPIs are presented in Figure 9-1.

Strategy CCUS Region KPIs (Discounted)

Analysis of the CCS system		Analysis of CO ₂ volumes (Mt)	
Total CCS value chain		Total CO ₂ Captured	1.274
CCS value chain (€/tonCO ₂ avoided)	-58.27	CO ₂ utilized	0.0
Total CAPEX per block		CO ₂ for mineralization (perm. avoided)	0.0
Cost of Capture (€/tonCO ₂ avoided)	-4.430	Stored	1.274
Cost of Transport (€/tonCO ₂ avoided)	0.000	Total emitted with CCS	0.142
Cost of Storage (€/tonCO ₂ avoided)	-0.117	Total avoided emission	1.256
OPEX per block		BIO CO ₂ captured, neg. Emissions	1.142
Cost of Capture (€/tonCO ₂ avoided)	-31.997	Total CO₂ fed into transport network	1.3
Cost of Transport (€/tonCO ₂ avoided)	-9.285	CCUS National Objectives	200
Cost of Storage (€/tonCO ₂ avoided)	-12.441	Share in national objectives	0.6 %
Transport cost (€/tonCO ₂ transported)	-9.2		
Utilisation (income from CO₂ sales) (M€)			
EUA/ETS credit savings in the region (M€)	0.0		

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Fig. 9-1: Overall scenario KPIs from Strategy CCUS tool.

Key outcomes are:

- A ton of CO₂ avoided is defined as total amount of CO₂ stored minus amount emitted during capture, transport and storage. In our scenario 1.274M tonnes of CO₂ were captured and stored, however, additional 0.142M tonnes were emitted in the process bringing the avoided emissions down to 1.274-0.142=1.256M tonnes.
- For the particular scenario OPEX dominates the picture with app. 92% of overall costs. Capture is the most expensive component, constituting 62% of total costs, see Fig. 9-2.

Fig. 9-2: Costs per each block of the value chain.

Second scenario evaluated was a Blue Hydrogen one. In this scenario remaining gas in Zar-3 field is produced during a 20 year period to generate hydrogen. Total production of hydrogen is around 30 000 tonnes or app. 3.7 tonnes produced daily accompanied by emission of comparable amount of CO₂ to the basecase scenario.

Economy wise the CAPEX is significantly increased with 100M Euro estimated investment into small Steam Methane Reforming plant and same as in basecase scenarios CAPEX of capture and storage.

We assume OPEX to stay the same, where reduction of the transport costs is „compensated“ by the SMR operational costs.

The total cost of avoided CO₂ ton is therefore drastically increases to 134 Euro / ton compared to basecase scenario of 58. However, we need to take the value of produced hydrogen into account. Table 9-1 shows the profit generated by Hydrogen sales and the final cost of the abated ton of CO₂ for different costs of Hydrogen.

Tab. 9-1: Hydrogen sales price, profit and final cost of a ton CO₂ abated

Hydrogen sale price	Profit	Cost of abated emissions
2 Euro / kg	50 Euro / ton of CO ₂	89 Euro / ton of CO ₂
5 Euro / kg	125 Euro / ton of CO ₂	9 Euro / ton of CO ₂

Finally, we have looked into possibility of a direct air capture (DAC) installed at the location. Using the publication by Izikowitz⁵ we end up of energy requirement of app. 2.5 kWh / kg CO₂ captured. With current emissions associated with energy production in Czech Republic⁶ of 415 g/kWh we end up with a scenario in which indirect emissions from DAC are actually comparable to the amount of CO₂ captured by it. This in the essence mean close to zero abated emissions and therefore very high costs per ton.

Once the DAC technology improves further, therefore reducing its energy consumption, and energy footprint in Czechia also decline, the DAC scenario becomes comparable in efficiency to the basecase one. Figure 9-3 shows DAC process efficiency (relationship of tonnes abated to tons emitted) as a function of energy emissions and energy requirement. The blue coloured section of the grid corresponds to the zone with process emitting more CO₂ than captured, red colour less than 50% process efficiency, green more than 50%. Blue dot shows efficiency of DAC in current Czech Republic conditions, red dots correspond to efficiency of basecase scenario.

For example with energy intensity of Norway or Iceland (29g/kwh⁷) DAC becomes more efficient than the basecase scenario with close to 93% of CO₂ abated compared to basecase scenario with its 88%.

⁵ https://www.researchgate.net/figure/Estimated-annualised-capital-Capex-and-operating-Opex-costs-for-a-solid-sorbent_fig2_350690343

⁶ <https://ourworldindata.org/grapher/carbon-intensity-electricity>

Fig. 9-3: Process efficiency (relationship of tonnes abated to tons emitted) as a function of energy emissions and energy requirement in DAC process. Blue colour corresponds to the zone with process emitting more CO₂ than captured, red colour less than 50% process efficiency, green more than 50%.

Since at the current conditions DAC implementation is technologically inefficient, its economic parameters were not estimated.

9.2 Design of facilities for pilot implementation (Task 8.2)

This task was carried out in tight coordination with pilot simulation activities carried out in WP3. Two transport and intermittent storage scenarios were originally evaluated based on an approx. 120 ton/day pilot injection scenario designed together with WP3. The EU pilot limit (100 000 tons) would then be reached in under 3 years of injection. The scenario assumes truck transport, using either cryogenic or high-pressure CO₂ transport. Figure 9-4 shows a possible transport route to site via route no.419.

Fig. 9-4: Potential truck route to site.

Scenario 1 assumes cryogenic transport of CO₂, using 14-ton trucks (requiring 9 trucks per day). However, as it a low pressure and temperature option (-30°C and 20 bar), it would require additional pumping and heating capacity to avoid hydrate and icing issues in the well and in the reservoir.

Scenario 2 is a high pressure system (200 bar, ambient temperature). The disadvantage here is that each truck can carry only 8 tons, bringing the total number of trucks per day to 15.

Setup showing both scenarios is shown in Figure 9-5.

Fig. 9-5: Scheme showing both low- and high-pressure gathering systems.

While both solutions having their positive sides, considering relatively small local roads the cryogenic solution is deemed the best as it allows for less trucks intervening with local traffic.

Estimation of capital and annual operating costs of required facilities have been conducted by MND. The estimates are presented in Tables 9-2 and 9-3. The costs presented here also lay foundation for economical estimates of storage costs in R8.3 Outcomes of full value chain analysis. It is important to state that the cost analysis was carried out in January 2024 and costs would need to be actualized prior to FID of the pilot project.

Tab. 9-2: Capital costs of the site facilities

CAPEX pilot test - raw estimation

	specification	cost
Unloading and Injection Facility	Constructions, Buildings	0 EUR
	Operation Units	
Main Facilities installation	<i>Pumping unit in container</i>	54 000 EUR
	<i>Heater (gas fired)</i>	34 000 EUR
Piping installations	<i>Piping</i>	5 000 EUR
	<i>Valves</i>	7 000 EUR
E&I installations	<i>MCC</i>	3 000 EUR
	<i>Cablings</i>	3 000 EUR
	<i>Earthing system</i>	500 EUR
	<i>Lighting</i>	500 EUR
	<i>Instrumentation</i>	12 000 EUR
	<i>Control/Safety system (DCS)</i>	5 000 EUR
Engineering/design		12 000 EUR
SUM		136 000 EUR

Tab. 9-3: Annual operational costs of the site facilities

OPEX pilot test - raw estimation

	specification (unit)	cost (EUR/unit)	year consumption (unit)	year cost
Utilities	Electricity (MWh)	180 EUR	500	89 964 EUR
	Gas (MWh)	75 EUR	1 184	88 830 EUR
	Transport (km)	2 EUR	220 500	352 800 EUR
	Rental (day)	135 EUR	350	47 250 EUR
Staff O&M	Manpower (day)	145 EUR	350	50 750 EUR
total				629 594 EUR

If CO₂ would need to be purchased for the pilot injection from the market its cost was estimated on a scale of 20M Euro. It is quite obvious that purchasing the CO₂ from the market will, most probably, kill the project. The only realistic solution is to form an early cooperation with a fitting emitter in order to pilot and demonstrate efficiency of the whole value chain, rather than only the storage site. A single point emitter identified in R8.4 can be approached together with other emitters in the area.

MND is currently considering co-generation unit utilizing the produced gas generating electricity and heat. However, for Zar-3 field such a unit will generate very small amount of CO₂ (on a scale of 1 ton per day), however it can contribute to reducing the energy consumption for heating the CO₂ as its heat as by product may be utilized to partially replace the heater required. This scenario should further be evaluated in more detail once plans for the co-generation unit are concretized.

Prior to pilot implementation it should be further investigated if there are local restrictions to trucks coming in the night and if the rush hours should be avoided. The findings should be reflected in changing suggested site facilities if deemed necessary.

9.3 Scenarios for future site development (Task 8.3)

During the project lifetime several different approaches to scenario building were discussed and various field development scenarios were considered. CCUS scenario can be built to answer a specific question on a different scale and with a different perspective. For example, scenarios created in the H2020 Strategy CCUS project focused on eight regions considered promising for carbon capture, utilisation, and storage (CCUS). I.e. they were built with a regional perspective. It is certainly possible to build a regional scenario for Moravia, as both emitters and storage sites identified by CGS and MND teams. However, in the current project, considering the focus on the Zar-3 site and the lack of experience with CO₂ storage in the Czech Republic, it is more sensible to build a scenario from the storage site perspective. The scenario, if realized, would demonstrate the feasibility and safety of CCUS in the region. Moreover, we have found that a regional scenario requires a separate, larger project, where both storage capacities of the fields in the area and long-term development strategies for the emitters need to be identified and put together. Otherwise, a long-term regional scenario becomes way too uncertain.

In developing the Zar3-centric scenario we have started with identifying its ultimate storage capacity. The value was found to be on the scale of app. 1M tonnes (see R8.4 for details) giving a storage capacity of ca 50 000 tonnes per annum for 20 years.

A pipeline transport is not feasible for the given CO₂ annual and ultimate storage volumes. The truck transport scenario, evaluated in deliverable V6, considered cryogenic tanks of 14 tonnes. Increasing the amount of truck deliveries from 9 for pilot scenario to 10 gives 140 tons daily at 100% operational efficiency or 51 100 tonnes annually, closely matching the above estimate. This scenario also implies a smooth expansion from pilot to full-field storage as they would require minimal changes to the infrastructure.

It should also be mentioned that if a regional storage scenario is developed later, the reservoir could be filled faster by, for example, including a local pipeline from, for example, a regional CO₂ hub. Alternatively, a 50 000 tpa injection rate could be sustained lowering transport costs by truck delivery from a local hub rather than a particular emitter.

Having a storage capacity we have identified three potential scenarios (their analysis is presented in section on Task 8.1, i.e. a single point industrial emitter, on-site blue hydrogen production and on-site direct air capture. In order to find a fitting emission site we have analysed the emitters with annual emissions on the scale of 50 000 tonnes. The Lihovar Kojetín bioethanol facility quickly stand out as the most promising candidate taking into account the following:

- Fitting emission scale.

- Short (straight line) distance of 40 km.
- Bioethanol production with relative low capture costs and long lifetime potential.

List of deliverables

Main results:

TO01000112-V2 Set of 3D models and maps with results of dynamic modelling of reservoir behaviour and pilot CO₂ injection – joint result of WP3 and WP8

TO01000112-V6 Pre-feasibility study of facilities for CO₂ injection

Other results:

R8.3 Outcomes of Full value chain analysis – report

R8.4 Scenarios for future site development

10 COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION

The main aim of project communication and dissemination activities is to create awareness of the existence of the project, disseminate project results to identified target groups to achieve the planned impact, raise general awareness of CCS as an important climate change mitigation technology and highlight the bilateral Czech-Norwegian cooperation based on project funding from Norway Grants.

10.1 Project events (Task 9.1)

On 5 March 2021, CGS organized the Project Launch event (result R9.3). The conference titled “Czech-Norwegian Cooperation on CCS” was, at the same time, the launch event of two CCS-related projects funded by Norway Grants and the Technology Agency of the Czech Republic within the KAPPA programme – CO₂-SPICER and METAMORPH.

The final conference (result R9.13) of the CO₂-SPICER project took place on 19 March at the Plaza Prague Hotel. During the conference, the results of scientific research on carbon dioxide storage in the rock environment were presented. The project was opened by Per Øystein Vatne, Chargé d'affaires of the Kingdom of Norway and Director of Exploration and Production of MND, Ms. Jana Hamršmídová.

10.2 Website (Task 9.2)

The project website at the address “<https://CO2-spicer.geology.cz>” was maintained in both Czech and English versions and updated during the whole project by adding fresh project news, promotion material, presentations from conferences and links to publications.

Fig. 10-1: CO₂-SPICER project website (updated English version) – subpage Downloads with a few examples of project communication outcomes.

10.3 Presentations and publications (Task 9.3)

In order to support the presentations and publication efforts of the project, CGS prepared a project graphic style package (result R9.4).

A project information leaflet (result R9.6) was created in cooperation of all Project Partners in December 2020. The leaflet is available in Czech and English versions, and was distributed in both electronic and printed forms. The leaflet is located on the Czech and English versions of the website at the following links:

- <https://CO2-spicer.geology.cz/cs/ke-stazeni>
- <https://CO2-spicer.geology.cz/en/downloads>

Press releases (result R9.7) was created in Czech and English versions. Press releases were distributed using the established communication channels of CGS (www.geology.cz, www.geology.cz/ccs) and Project Partners. The press releases was further offered to the media and published on the project website at:

- <https://CO2-spicer.geology.cz/cs/ke-stazeni> (Czech version)
- <https://CO2-spicer.geology.cz/en/downloads> (English version)

During the projects was created in cooperation of CGS with all Project Partners three issues of the project newsletters (result R9.11). The newsletter was prepared in Czech version only (as planned) and was distributed in electronic and printed forms. It is also available on project website at:

- <https://CO2-spicer.geology.cz/cs/ke-stazeni>

Project and its results were presented at more than 12 international conferences. Here are some selected:

- **Comparison of two candidate hydrocarbon fields for a CO₂ storage pilot in the Czech Republic.** Presentation of results of CO₂-SPICER, REPP-CO₂ and ENOS projects at the 2nd EAGE Geoscience and Engineering for the Energy Transition Conference (GET2021); online (November 2021). Authors: V. Hladík, R. Prochác, M. Pereszlényi (CGS), R. Berenblyum, A. Shchipanov, A. Nermoen, E.P. Ford (NORCE).
- **CO₂-SPICER: Czech-Norwegian project to prepare a CO₂ storage pilot in a carbonate reservoir.** Presentation of the CO₂-SPICER project at the 11th Trondheim CCS conference (TCCS-11); online (June 2021). Authors: V. Hladík, R. Prochác, P. Jirman (CGS), V. Opletal, M. Pagáč (MND), R. Berenblyum, A. Shchipanov, E. Ford, A. Nermoen (NORCE).
- **Diagenesis and dolomitization of Jurassic carbonate rocks in the SE Bohemian Massif.** Presentation of research results related to Jurassic carbonates, including CO₂-SPICER project, WP5, at the 35th IAS Meeting of Sedimentology; online (June 2021). Authors: J. Franců, L. Jurenka, P. Jirman (CGS).
- **Assessment of trans-boundary effects at LBr-1 CO₂ storage pilot site and regulatory solutions.** Presentation of results of REPP-CO₂, ENOS and CO₂-SPICER projects at the 15th Greenhouse Gas Control Technologies conference (GHGT-15); online (March 2021). Authors: V. Hladík, J. Franců, V. Kolečka, M. Pereszlényi (CGS), L. Kollbotn, E. Ford (NORCE), M. Jankulár (ŠGÚDŠ), M. Koenen (TNO).
- **CO₂ storage pilot project in a depleting hydrocarbon field in Czechia**
Presentation of CO₂-SPICER project results at the 15th CO₂GeoNet Open Forum; Venice (September 2022). Authors: V. Hladík, R. Prochác (CGS), V. Opletal, M. Pagáč (MND) & the CO₂-SPICER project team.
- **CO₂-SPICER - CO₂ Storage Pilot In a CarbonatE Reservoir**
Presentation of the CO₂-SPICER project at the 55th Continental European Energy Council meeting; Praha (October 2022). Authors: V. Opletal, L. Klímová (MND), V. Hladík, J. Rez (CGS).
- **Assessment of a mature hydrocarbon field in SE Czech Republic for a CO₂ storage pilot**
Presentation of CO₂-SPICER project results at the 16th Greenhouse Gas Control Technologies conference (GHGT-16); Lyon (October 2022). Authors: V. Hladík, R. Prochác, P. Jirman (CGS), V. Opletal (MND), R. Berenblyum, A. Shchipanov, A. Nermoen, E. P. Ford (NORCE), M. Matloch Porzer (VSB) & the CO₂-SPICER project team (Fig. 2.9-3).
- **Basin modelling of a pilot CO₂ storage in a dolomite reservoir, Bohemian Massif, Czech Republic.**
Presentation of the CO₂-SPICER project results at the Petroleum Systems Technology Days 2022; Aachen. (August 2022). Authors: J. Franců, R. Prochác, P. Jirman, L. Jurenka, J. Vácha, V. Hladík (CGS), V. Opletal (MND), W. Wheeler (NORCE).

- **TCCS-12 – 12th Trondheim Conference on CO₂ Capture, Transport and Storage. June, 2023, Trondheim, Norway (Fig. 10-2):**
 1. **Preparing for CO₂ pilot in the Czech Republic.** TCCS-12. Authors: R. Berenblyum, V. Hladík†, J. Franců, M. Pereszlényi, E. Hudečková, V. Kolečka, V. Opletal, M. Pagáč, A. Shchipanov, A. Nermoen, E. Ford, P. Jirman, M. Klempa, P. Kolář.
 2. **Seasonal climatic constraints of soil-gas baseline monitoring at the Zar-3 pilot CO₂ storage site, Czechia.** TCCS-12. Authors: P. Jirman, J. Franců, V. Hladík †, P. Pařízek.
 3. **Risk and reliability analyses: Examples of applications focusing on P&A and CO₂ storage.** TCCS-12. Author: Eric Patrick Ford (NORCE).
 4. **Rock strengths and Earth stresses – assessing safe operation envelope during CO₂ storage in a mature oil and gas field.** TCCS-12. Authors: A. Nermoen, M. M. Porzer, J. Sa Sancer, A. Shchipanov, V. Hladik, M. Klempa.
 5. **Decision making under uncertainty case study from a Czech Republic CO₂ storage.** TCCS-12. Authors: E. P. Ford, A. Nermoen , H. P. Lohne, A. Shchipanov, R. Berenblyum , M. M. Porzer.
 6. **Single-cell reservoir model for CO₂ storage planning.** TCCS-12. Authors: A. Khrulenko and R. Berenblyum (NORCE).
- **IMOG – 31st International Meeting on Organic Geochemistry (IMOG), 10-15 September, 2023, Montpellier, France:**
 1. **Seal efficiency evaluation in the Zar-3 pilot CCS using biomarkers, mudlogs and isotopes in reservoir and caprocks, SE Czechia.** IMOG. Authors: J. Franců, D. Ocásková, M. Pereszlényi, P. Pařízek, P. Jirman, R. Prochác, V. Hladík†
 2. **Soil gas monitoring experience from above underground gas storage and a pilot CO₂ storage, Czechia.** IMOG, Authors: J. Franců, P. Jirman, V. Hladík†
- **GeoNet – 16th CO₂ GeoNet Open Forum, 2-5 October, 2023, San Servolo, Venice, Italy:**
 1. **Preparatory work for CO₂ pilot injection into naturally fractured carbonate reservoir in the Czech Republic.** GeoNet, Authors: M. Pagac, P. Jirman, M. Libcinska, R. Berenblyum, A. Nermoen, E. P. Ford.
 2. **Carbon storage in dolomite reservoir: rock-fluid-CO₂ interactions.** GeoNet, Authors: J. Vácha, Š. Káňa, L. Jurenka, J. Franců, M. Klempa.
- **ICMRI 2023 – International Conference On Multidisciplinary Research And Innovation. 9-10.April, 2023, Istanbul, Turkey:**
 1. **Study of mechanical-elastic parameters of reservoir rocks with respect to the purpose of permanent CO₂ storage.** ICMRI 2023. Authors: A. Lacman, M. Křístek, P. Žilová and M. Klempa.

Fig. 10-2: TCCS-12 – 12th Trondheim Conference on CO₂ Capture, Transport and Storage. June, 2023, Trondheim, Norway.

All project presentations and publications are available on project website at <https://co2-spicer.geology.cz/en/downloads>.

An important part of communication activities was the liaison with other projects funded by EEA/Norway Grants. Within the continued partnership with the CCS4CEE project (Building momentum for the long-term CCS deployment in the CEE region), funded from the Fund for Regional Cooperation of EEA/Norway Grants, CO₂-SPICER coordinator provided consultations and input to the National CCS roadmap for the Czech Republic that was prepared by EUROPEUM – the Czech partner of the CCS4CEE project. A presentation was made on ‘Potential of the Czech Republic for geological storage of CO₂’ at the National CCS seminar organised by EUROPEUM on the occasion of launching the Czech CCS roadmap in Prague.

Communication activities addressing industrial stakeholders included a series of bilateral consultations, both face-to-face and online, that were devoted to possibilities of utilisation of CCS technology as a solution for reduction of CO₂ emissions from industrial facilities, sharing information about the CO₂-SPICER project, discussions on future utilisation of its results and possible participation of the industry representatives in CO₂-SPICER *End-User Group*. The consulted companies included Českomoravský Cement a.s., ČD Cargo, SMOLO a.s. and Lafarge Cement Čížkovice. Consultations were also provided to the Ministry of Industry and Trade and the Ministry of Environmental of the Czech Republic. A report “Introduction to CO₂ Storage in geological formations in the Czech Republic and neighbouring countries: Implications for the lime production of Vápenka Čertovy Schody, a.s., Lhoist Central Europe, Tmář u Berouna” was prepared by J. Franců and M. Pereszlenyi for the Association of Lime Producers in the CR in September 2023.

University students form an important target group of project communication. In 2021, VŠB – the project partner attracted four students of the university (VŠB – Technical University of Ostrava) to participate in the research dealt with in the CO₂-SPICER and prepare their final theses.

CO₂-SPICER project implementation attracted relatively high media interest. Information about the project, its objectives, status of solution, but also the overall status and perspectives of the CCS technology both in Czechia and worldwide were the main topics of interest. Written information, as well as interviews with journalists were provided to media. Not only thematically profiled media, but also those with nationwide coverage were interested in the project. In total, information about the project appeared in the media more than 40 times. Examples are shown in Figs. 10-3 to 10-6.

Fig. 10-3: Samples of articles in the media.

ekolist.cz / zpravodajství / zprávy

titulní strana | zpravodajství | publicistika | zelená domácnost | kultura | kalendář akcí | fotobank

zprávy | tiskové zprávy | co píší jiní | speciály

Roste globální zájem o technologie na zachytávání oxidu uhličitého. První projekt se chystá i v Česku

20.10.2021 01:19 | PRAHA (ČTK)
» Diskuse: 8

Technologie CCS společnosti Shell Scotford, Fort Saskatchewan, Alberta
Licence | © © © Některá práva vyhrazena
Foto | Roberta Franchuk, Pembina Institute / Flickr

Roste globální zájem o technologie na zachytávání a ukládání oxidu uhličitého (CO₂). Podle nejnovější zprávy mezinárodního think-tanku Global CCS Institute se celkový počet komerčních projektů ve fázi přípravy a provozu letos zvýšil o 71 na 135, tedy o 90 procent. Plně v provozu je podle ní 27 zařízení, čtyři jsou ve výstavbě a 102 v různých fázích přípravy. První pilotní projekt se chystá také v Česku.

ROZHOVOR

Bez ukládání CO₂ klimatické neutrality nedosáhneme

I Redakce OF

Pro technologie CCS (carbon capture and storage) zatím neexistuje „business case“, přinejmenším v evropských podmínkách. Náklady na takto odstraněnou jednu tunu CO₂ jsou pořád vyšší než cena emisní povolenky. Ta se ovšem bude do budoucna zvyšovat a jakmile převyší úroveň nákladů, technologie se stane rentabilní a začne se mnohem více prosazovat. O perspektivě CCS jsme hovořili s Vitem Hladíkem z České geologické služby.

ENERGETIKA

VRAŤ SE POD ZEM

V Česku vzniká unikátní projekt na podzemní ukládání emisí z průmyslu

Petr Weiskert
Kjetil Alvik

Za bývalou železnu opomenu ještě podobný projekt neexistoval. V Česku se začne reálně zkoumat dožehované ložisko ropu a zemního plynu proto, aby se otáčovalo, jak pod zem dostat oxid uhličitý. Mělo to zůstat na první poslech banální, ale ve hře je zrod úplně nového byznysu pro těžařské firmy, a hlavně evropské miliardy, které poputují v příštích letech na ochranu klimatu. Právě oxid uhličitý mají zachytávat největší znečišťovatelé a hledá se, kam s ním.

Znovu ve hře
Pro laješmoky z oboru nejde o nic převratného. O pozemním ukládání oxidu uhličitého se v Česku hovoří již před třiceti lety a podobně jako v jiných zemích se přišlo na to, že je to myšlenka sice zajímavá, ale také hodně drahá. Aby nevyspávala, největší znečišťovatelé, jako

Jednou ze zmi, kde se zachytává a ukládá oxid uhličitý, je Norsko, kde skleníkový plyn putuje pod mořské dno.

Přesné v této době přichází Česká geologická služba s projektem CO₂-SPICER. Podílí se na něm i akademická síla, financovaná poskytl norské fondy

ložiska se totiž dají použít netežko uhlé sloje, což už je pro Česko zajímavější nápad. Vhodné geologické podmínky pro ukládání by mohly být třeba i ve středních a východních Čechách, přičemž tam ale neprobíhá, protože nic „zařizovat“ pro potřeby průmyslu tam pod zemí nikdy nebylo. Ještě pro ukládní dojde, že CO₂ se ukládá v hloubkách

MLADÁ FRONTA DNES | čtvrtek 29. 4. 2021

Brno a jižní Morava

20 °C | 7 °C

Počasí v kraji více informací →
pocasi.dnes.cz

DNES Brno, Blansko, Břeclav, Hodonín, Vyškov, Znojmo

Oxid uhličitý ukryjí do ropného vrtu

Na jižní Moravě vzniká první podzemní úložiště CO₂ ve východní a střední Evropě. „Problémový“ plyn do něj uloží třeba teplárny.

Světový boom Oxid uhličitý, vypouštěný velkými průmyslovými provozy, se ukládá do hornin hluboko pod zem pomocí vrtů. Ilustrace foto: ČTK

Zachycování uhlíku může prodloužit životnost uhelných elektráren. Rozhovor s šéfkou ...
Článek

SZ | Seznam Zprávy

00:26 / 18:22

Uhlík je třeba dostat zpátky pod zem. Evropská Zelená dohoda se bez technologie CCS neobejde, říká Vít Hladík

VITĚCH KRISTEN

Fig. 10-4: Samples of articles in the media.

Fig. 10-5: Samples of articles on CCS in the Czech media.

Fig. 10-6: Apple Podcast on Seznam.cz – Geological CO₂ storage, interview by Juraj Franců, CGS (in Czech).

An overview of project media coverage is available on project website (Czech version) at <https://CO2-spicer.geology.cz/cs/zajimave-odkazy>.

An article about the CO₂-SPICER project was published in the online version of the VSB-TUO Akademik University Newsletter (<https://www.vsb.cz/magazin/cs/detail-novinky?reportId=46507>).

List of deliverables

Main results:

TO01000112-V7 Final technical report of the CO₂-SPICER project

TO01000112-V8 Manuscript of article showcasing CO₂-SPICER project results submitted for publication in a peer-reviewed journal

Other results:

R9.3 Project launch event

R9.4 Project graphic style package

R9.5 Updated Communication plan

R9.6 Project information leaflet

R9.7 Press releases

9.8 Project website in CZ and EN

9.9 Posters, oral presentations and abstracts published in proceedings at national and international events – track record on project website

R9.10 Article in popular science journal

R9.11 Project newsletter – 3 issues

R9.12 Czech-Norwegian CCS workshop held in Norway

R9.13 Final project conference

11 PROJECT MANAGEMENT AND REPORTING

The main goal of this project part (WP 10) was to ensure that the project ran as smoothly as possible. The project management structure, as well as the duties at different management levels were defined with a great attention to detail already during the project preparation stage, and have been incorporated in the Project Contract and the Partnership Agreement. This work covered all project management and other related tasks – organisation of project meetings, review meetings, administrative matters, reporting to and cooperation with the Programme Operator and individual Project partners, economic management etc.

11.1 Project and Work Package Coordination and Management (Task 10.1)

This Task included the management of the project and its key activities by the Project coordinator and leaders of the 10 defined Work Packages (WP1-WP10). In addition, it also covered the work of the project's three governing bodies – the General Assembly, Management Board and End-User Group.

The General Assembly was the highest decision-making body of the project. All partners involved in the project had one representative in the General Assembly, their respective voting powers (number of votes) was corresponding to the scope of the partner's involvement in the project (in person-months of work). The General Assembly met four times (one meeting per year); meetings were planned to be held in the form of a personal meeting as a part of the project meeting. The first meeting was held online due to travel restrictions in the COVID pandemic situation, the others were held in person at the partners' domiciles, i.e. in Brno (2022), Hodonín (2023) and Praha (2023).

The Management Board supported the Project coordinator in operative project management. It consisted of the Project coordinator (Principal investigator) and the Work Packages leaders. In addition, the representatives of Project Partners also participated in Management Board meetings to ensure smooth flow of information across the whole project team. Throughout project duration Management Board used to meet regularly once a month (usually on every second Thursday of each month with a few exceptions) mainly in the form of teleconferences, several meetings were arranged as physical meetings within the project meeting held for a larger group of researchers.

The formation of the End-User Group and negotiations with interested parties began in 2023. The candidates included industrial companies interested in CCS technology and policy makers. At the Final project conference in Prague in March 2024, stakeholders consisting of representatives from the Lime Producers Association CR, Gas Storage CZ, UNIGEO and Heidelberg Materials CZ (ČM cement) established the End-User Group.

Task 10.1 covered also the preparation and organisation of project meetings. In addition to the first two online meetings in 2020 and 2021 (COVID restrictions), the other four project meetings were organised in person with the possibility of online connection for those participants who could not participate face-to-face. The project meetings were held one by one in Bergen and Brno in 2022 and in Hodonín and Ostrava in 2023. In all cases, several WPs or topic-related joint workshops (modelling, future scenarios, geochemistry and geomechanics, risk assessment) were affiliated with the project meetings as needed.

11.2 Project Administration, Liaison with Programme Operator, Reporting (Task 10.2)

The purpose of this Task was to provide administrative support to the project management team, both during routine, day-to-day operations and in the preparation of interim reports and the final report. The Task covered also the practical aspect of ongoing cooperation with the Programme Operator (TA CR) and the preparation of projects reports by the Project coordinator, WP leaders and Project Partners.

A total of three interim annual reports were submitted each January of the following year, the Project final report will be submitted in June 2024 after the end of the project. In compiling the report, the information provided at a special TA CR webinars and gradually provided more detailed information were used.

In frame of cooperation with the Programme Operator several monitoring visits, audits and on-line consultation were held.

An important part of the project administration efforts are the public procurement procedures to accommodate the planned sub-contracts, purchases of materials and services needed by the project in full compliance with applicable regulations (in particular applicable public procurement legislation and internal procurement policies of all partners).

Two public tenders “Feasibility study on the applicability of seismic survey for monitoring of the CO₂ plume at Zar-3” and “Well integrity logging” were organized. Other purchases of material and services were carried out using the usual procedures of Project Partners.

11.3 Economic and financial management of the project (Task 10.3)

This task included the financial reporting in accordance with the Fund Operator’s policies as well as preparation of documents and other materials for monitoring reports and, where relevant, audits and inspections. During all project actual costs and expenses has been continuously compared with approved budget. All partners were responsible for regular transfers of economic data to the project administrator.

Actual project costs for the year were reported in the annual interim reports submitted in January of the following year, including relevant documents and other materials. Project final report will be submitted in June 2024.

List of deliverables

Other results:

R10.1 Meeting minutes from Project meetings, General Assembly and End-User group meetings

R10.2 Project interim reports in ISTA

R10.3 Project final report in ISTA

R10.4 Documentation of public tenders

12 CONCLUSION

The essence of the CO₂-SPICER project was to perform the preparatory work for a CO₂ storage pilot project, the first in Central and Eastern Europe, in a mature and depleted oil and gas field in the SE Czech Republic. The achieved project results may serve as ready-made input required by the legislation for the implementation follow-up activities. CO₂-SPICER significantly increased the Technology Readiness Level of CO₂ geological storage in the Czech Republic and made an important step towards practical deployment of the CCS technology. The key research partners CGS and NORCE had a long record of joint research activities. Both organisations have been members of the CO₂GeoNet – the European network of excellence on geological storage of CO₂ and have, together, closely cooperated in a number of international projects including in Norway Grants (projects TOGEOS and REPP-CO₂) and Horizon 2020 programme (project ENOS).

The key results of the CO₂-SPICER project activities include:

- 3D static geological model of the storage complex
- 3D dynamic model of reservoir behaviour and simulation of fluid flow verified by the match of modelled and real oil and gas production history. Based on that, predictions were simulated of the future CO₂ injection into the reservoir, growth of the stored CO₂ plume and related pressure and temperature effects in the Storage complex. A manuscript of a paper was submitted to MDPI Energies journal.
- Geomechanical characteristics of the reservoir and seal rocks using ultrasonic stiffness and strength provided basis for the conclusions on the failure envelope describing the conditions necessary to keep the storage of the injected CO₂ safe. The effect of changes in fluid pressure during storage and the effect of cooling by the cold supercritical CO₂ were evaluated in respect to changes in the effective stress.
- Geochemical properties of the fluids, microbial consortia, reservoir rocks and caprocks were interpreted from the points of view of the depositional environment, origin, diagenesis, reactivity and type of porosity. The CO₂-fluid-rock interactions were characterised using the reaction chambers and modelling. The most important chemical processes included dissolution of carbonate cements due to acidification of the formation water during the injection of CO₂ into the reservoir. The formation of secondary carbonates were predicted for the remote future. Minor porosity changes were predicted by the models associated with the CO₂ injection to the reservoir. The results were used in the dynamic modelling and risk assessment.
- Risk assessment was evaluated using the geochemistry, geomechanics and well integrity logging. It covered identification of hazards related to CO₂ leakage from the storage site, such as potential leakage pathways, flux rates, critical controls and secondary effects of storage of CO₂ and other factors which could pose a hazard to human health or the environment.
- Three years of field baseline monitoring included the soil gas geochemistry, seismology, ground water measurements and shallow ground water modelling. Feasibility study on applicability of seismic methods for CO₂ plume monitoring was carried out using the static and dynamic models. The experience was

incorporated in the Storage site monitoring plan, which consisted of the pre-storage, operational and post-storage phases.

- Scenarios of the future development included design of the surface and subsurface facilities for the selected pilot Zar-3 site. The whole value chain analysis identified potential gaps between the costs associated with capture, transport and site development costs.
- The project outreach was performed through three CGS CO₂-SPICER Newsletters, two press releases, radio interview and VSB-TUO Akademik University Newsletter.
- Czech-Norwegian cooperation in the area of CCS was intensified by cooperative research of Czech and Norwegian partners, joint presentations at the Final Project Conference in Prague and all the previous conferences, meetings, as well as through liaison with other Czech-Norwegian projects funded from EEA/Norway Grants.

In summary, the results of the CO₂-SPICER project goals were successfully completed and the scientific papers are being handled by the Editorial offices. Communication with the End-User Group has been intensified, some of them contributed to the Final project conference in Praha in March 2024.

This report is a result of the CO₂-SPICER project
(CO₂ Storage Pilot In a CarbonatE Reservoir) - project No: TO01000112.

The CO₂-SPICER project benefits from a €2.32 mil grant
from Norway and Technology Agency of the Czech Republic.

More information about the project can be found at
CO2-spicer.geology.cz.

PROJECT PARTNERS

COORDINATOR

T A
Č R
